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HOFFMANN, C., KÜHNERT, T., LIESS, M., RUSSEL, D.J., SCHULZ, S.,
SPECKA, X., SVOBODA, N., ZOARDER, M.A.M., HEINRICH, U.

Report on available soil data for German agricultural areas (2018)

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Editor: BonaRes Centre for Soil Research
c/o Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ
Department of Soil System Science
Theodor-Lieser-Str. 4 | 06120 Halle (Saale), Germany
Phone: (+49) 345 558 5226 | E-Mail: info@bonares.de
www.bonares.de

Title Report on available soil data for German agricultural areas (2018)

Authors Stein, Susanne – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Eberhardt, Einar – Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR), Hannover;

Grosse, Meike – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Helming, Katharina – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Hierold, Wilfried – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Hoffmann, Carsten – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Kühnert, Thomas – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Ließ, Mareike – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ (UFZ), Halle (Saale);

Russell, David J. – Senckenberg Museum of Natural History (SGN), Görlitz;

Schulz, Sina – Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR), Hannover;

Specka, Xenia – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Svoboda, Nikolai – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Zoarder, M.A. Muqit – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg;

Heinrich, Uwe – Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg

Correspondence susanne.stein@zalf.de

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Abstract

One task of the BonaRes Data Centre is to support the research projects of the BonaRes funding initiative in the detection and reuse of geospatial soil data for Germany from different sources such as public authorities, state agencies or research institutions. This report provides an overview of available soil data from survey programs as well as derived data products with information about data lineage and access. In case of specific characteristics of the data concerning the validity, completeness, currentness or resolution, these are mentioned to estimate the reusability. The data sources are further evaluated in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Keywords

BonaRes, soil science, agricultural science, agronomy, research data, data provision, data interoperability, data availability, FAIR principles

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Introduction

The BonaRes-Centre plays a central role within the German research initiative BonaRes (*Soil as a Sustainable Resource for the Bioeconomy*) and has the goal to improve the scientific basis for sustainable soil management and to support the associated research projects to do so. This includes the provision of information about the availability and accessibility of soil related geospatial data¹ for agricultural areas in form of a report. Further, characteristics and limitations of the datasets concerning the validity, completeness and currentness as well as specifics of the data lineage shall be provided. So, the readers can estimate the reusability of the data for their purpose.

The spatial frame of the national research initiative BonaRes is Germany. Due to that, the report considers solely geospatial data which have a spatial link to the area of Germany. The aim of the report is to draw a comprehensive picture of the soil data available for the whole area in consistent quality and to supplement this picture by other datasets at the regional or local level. Maps with a smaller scale than 1:1,000,000 were considered as too coarse to support the projects issues and are therefore excluded. To meet the scientific demand for area-wide data with a consistent methodology, the presented data must cover at least the area of one German federal state. Datasets which cover less than 2/3 of the agricultural area of one federal state were not considered. The datasets within each chapter are arranged from small scale to large scale. The selection of the point data presented here do not follow these spatial criteria. Point data related to observation programs with regional dimension or coarse survey raster (up to 16 km) were included to give a complete picture of the available soil survey data.

The first chapter concerns sample and survey data of the topsoil and soil profiles and presents point datasets with a range of measured soil parameters. Derived or modelled data and map products with specific thematic focus (e.g. field capacity or nitrate retention capacity) were assigned to the second chapter. The information was mainly obtained from institutional websites and by contacting the persons in charge via e-mail or telephone.

To enhance the readability of the report, an overview table of all data was put at the beginning, followed by the detailed descriptions of the single datasets. The overview table includes the title of the dataset (*Data object/ data repository*), the *Geospatial frame*², the *Publisher*³ and the *Year of publication* of the dataset. The column *Geospatial frame* includes information about the area, where the data are related to, while it was distinguished between global data (for the total global land surface) and international (for point data distributed worldwide). The column *Geometry* distinguishes between Raster⁴ and the geographic features Polygon, Point and Line. Information about the data access (free/ not fee) is addressed in the overview table and, additionally, in the detailed descriptions. While the latter includes information about the reuse conditions, the format, the

¹ According to the definition of “geospatial data” by the [Open Geospatial Consortium \(OGC\)](#) Glossary of Terms, 2018.

² The acronyms of the Federal State of Germany are in accordance with the ISO 3166-2:DE

³ Institution acronyms are listed in the chapter Acronyms

⁴ “digital representation of the extent of geographic datasets using “grid-cells” in a matrix”, PreANVIL Glossary

geodata-URL and the data hosting repository, the overview table column *Free access* distinct between free ('yes') and not free access ('no'). Free access means barrier-free data provision via URL (geodata link or Web Feature Service) at the website of the data providing institution or data infrastructure or sent by e-mail after request. User registration is not defined as access barrier here. The column *Resolution/ Scale* concerns the spatial resolution of the data e.g. the size of the regular grid-cell for raster data or the scale for vector data. For point data the column *H/S/M* specifies whether the soil profile data include horizon data (H) or one parameter per profile (S = Single) or more than one parameter per profile (M = Multiple). For the derived data and map products the column *WMS* is marked with an X if a Web Map Service (OGC-Standard for the provision of georeferenced map images via the internet) is available.

The evaluation of the presented datasets was made by applying the FAIR principles, which concern requirements for the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of research data and data infrastructures (Wilkinson, M. D. et al. 2016). The FAIR Principles are a minimal set of community-agreed guiding principles that data and their metadata should follow to enhance the discovery and reuse of the data. They are applied within the GO FAIR initiative and a European Commission Group in the frame of the establishment of the European Open Science Cloud (Hodson, J. et al., 2018). **Findability** is given when the dataset has an identifier, rich metadata description and is presented in a searchable infrastructure like a data portal. To improve the **Accessibility** of the data, their metadata should be accessible via a standardized and universally implementable communication protocol (e.g. http(s) or ftp) which includes machine readable information about the access requirements. The data access itself is no requirement, but the clear information about the access conditions. That includes also the persistence of the metadata. **Interoperability** targets the (programming) language and vocabulary of data and metadata which should be community-shared and accessible for humans as well as for computers. **Reusability** is enhanced when the data are supplemented by qualified information about the data lineage and generation which enable the user to determine the usability of the data. Further, the license and acknowledgement conditions should be clear and the dataset should be in a sustainable file format which meets community standards. The last column in the overview table shows which of the four principles is fulfilled. Many data missing a clear story of the origin history and lineage, so the principle Reusability is often not fulfilled. A full Interoperability by machine-readable metadata is also not given in several cases.

The overview table is followed by the single chapters with more detailed information about the datasets access conditions (supplemented by an URL) and a general description of the dataset and its lineage. If the data have characteristics or limitations concerning the completeness, currentness, validity, resolution, interoperability or reusability these were also specified in the detailed remarks. If comprehensive supplementary material is provided by the data publisher, it is noted under the point *Supplement*.

Overview table

ID	Data object/ data repository	Geospatial frame	Publisher	Year publ.	Geometry	Resolution/ Scale	H/S/M	Free access	FAIR
1.1 Soil sample and survey data - Topsoil and surface data									
1.1.1	International Soil Moisture Network – Datasets	International	ISMN	-	Point	5'	H/S	X	FR
1.1.2	FLUXNET – network of eddy covariance sites	International	U.S. Dep. of Energy	2007/2015	Point	-	S	X	FAIR
1.1.3	ICOS Carbon Portal - Datasets	Europe	ICOS	2015	Point	-	S/M	X	FAIR
1.1.4	LUCAS topsoil survey 2009	Europe	JRC	2013	Point	-	M	X	FAR
1.1.5	German weather station data – soil temperature	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Point	-	H/S	X	IR
1.1.6	TERENO-Observatory data	Sites in Germany	FZ Jülich	2008	Point	-	S/M	X	FAIR
1.1.7	Edaphobase	Germany	SGN		Point	-	S/M	X	FAIR
1.1.8	Exploratories for Biodiversity - Datasets	Sites in Germany	Fr.-Schiller- Univ. Jena	2008	Point	-	S	X	AR
1.2 Soil sample and survey data - Soil Profile Data									
1.2.1	WoSIS Soil Profile Database	International	ISRIC	2016	Point	-	M	X	FAI
1.2.2	European Soil Database v2.0 – Soil Profile Analytical Database	Europe, Eurasia	JRC	2004	Point	-	H	X	FAR
1.2.3	Laboratory and Profile Database BGR	Germany	BGR	-	Point	-	H/S/M		R
1.2.4	German Agricultural Soil Inventory	Germany	TI	2018	Point	8x8 km grid	H		R
1.2.5	Soil profile data for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	-	Point	-	H/S		-
1.2.6	Soil profile data for Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2018	Point	-		X*	R
1.2.7	Soil profile data for Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	-	Point	-			R
1.2.8	Soil profile data for Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	-	Point	-			-
1.2.9	Soil profile data for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	-	Point	-		X	AR
1.2.10	Soil profile data for Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	-	Point	-			R
1.2.11	Soil profile data for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	LANUV	2016	Point	-		X	AR
1.2.12	Soil profile data for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	-	Point	-			R
1.2.13	Soil profile data for Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	-	Point	-			-
1.2.14	Soil profile data for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2018	Point	-		X*	AR
1.2.15	Soil profile data for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	-	Point	-			R
1.2.16	Soil profile data for Schleswig-Holstein	DE-SH	LLUR	-	Point	-			-
1.2.17	Soil profile data for Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	-	Point	-			R
1.2.18	Long-term soil monitoring Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LUBW	-	Point	-		X*	R
1.2.19	Long-term soil monitoring Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	-	Point	-		X*	R
1.2.20	Long-term soil monitoring Brandenburg	DE-BB	LfU-BB	2017	Point	-	S	X	R
1.2.21	Long-term soil monitoring Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	-	Point	-			-
1.2.22	Long-term soil monitoring Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2012/2015	Point	-		X*	R
1.2.23	Long-term soil monitoring	DE-MV	LUNG	-	Point	-			-

	Mecklenburg-W Pomerania									
1.2.24	Long-term soil monitoring North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	LANUV	2005/2009	Point	-			X*	R
1.2.25	Long-term soil monitoring Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2012	Point	-			X*	R
1.2.26	Long-term soil monitoring Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2006	Point	-			X*	R
1.2.27	Long-term soil monitoring Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2015	Point	-			X	R
1.2.28	Long-term soil monitoring Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAU	2017	Point	-			X	R
1.2.29	Long-term soil monitoring Schleswig-Holstein	DE-SH	LLUR	2014	Point	-			X*	R
1.2.30	Long-term soil monitoring Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	2006	Point	-			X	R
<i>ID</i>	<i>Data object</i>	<i>Geospatial frame</i>	<i>Publisher</i>	<i>Year publ.</i>	<i>Geometry</i>	<i>Resolution/ Scale</i>	<i>WMS</i>	<i>Free access</i>	<i>FAIR</i>	
2.1 Soil map products – Basic soil properties										
2.1.1	Harmonized World Soil Database v1.2	Global	FAO	2012	Raster DB	30"			X	FAIR
2.1.2	SoilGrids	Global	ISRIC	2014	Raster	1 km; 250 m			X	FAI
2.1.3	European Soil Database v2.0 – Soil Geographical Database	Europe, Eurasia	JRC	2004 (raster 2006)	Polygon/ Raster	1:1,000,000 1 km			X	FAR
2.1.4	Land use-stratified soil map of Germany (BÜK1000N)	Germany	BGR	2005	Polygon	1:1,000,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.5	Soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200)	Germany	BGR / SGD	1998-2018	Polygon	1:200,000			X	FAIR
2.1.6	General geological map of the Federal Republic of Germany (GÜK200)	Germany	BGR / SGD	2007	Polygon	1:200,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.7	Medium-scale Agricultural Site Mapping (MMK)	Eastern Germany	FZB	1981	Polygon	1:100,000	X	for BB		R
2.1.8	Soil map BK50 (GeoLa) for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2012	Polygon	1:50,000	X			FA
2.1.9	General soil map 1:25 000 (ÜBK25) for Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2013	Polygon	1:25,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.10	Soil-geological map (BK50) for Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	in process	Polygon	1:50,000			X	FAIR
2.1.11	Areal soil data (BFD50) for Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	2002	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.12	Soil map (BK50) for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2017	Polygon	1:50,000	X			FAIR
2.1.13	'Konzeptbodenkarte' (KBK25) Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	1996/2017	Polygon	1:25,000				-
2.1.14	Soil map 1:50,000 (IS BK 50) for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	X	FAI
2.1.15	Soil map 1:5,000 (IS BK 5) for agricultural areas in North Rhine-Westphalia	1/2 of DE-NW	GD-NW	2001-2018	Polygon	1:5,000	X			FAI
2.1.16	Soil map 1:100,000 (BÜK100) Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2001	Polygon	1:10,000	X	X	X	FA
2.1.17	Digital soil map 1:50,000 (BK50/digBK50) for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2012	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.18	Provisional soil map 1:50,000 (VBK50) for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2012	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	X	FAIR
2.1.19	Soil-geological survey map (BGKK100) for Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	2000	Polygon	1: 100,000				-
2.3 Soil map products – Soil Hydrology										
2.3.1	A global dataset of soil hydraulic	Global	Montzka,	2017	Raster	0.25°			X	FAIR

	properties and sub-grid variability of soil water retention and hydraulic conductivity curves			C. et al.					
2.3.2	ESA Climate Change Initiative - Soil Moisture (CCI SM v04.4)	Global	ESA	2018	Raster	0.25°		X	AR
2.3.3	3D Soil Hydraulic Database of Europe	Europe	JRC	2017	Raster	1 km; 250 m		X	FAR
2.3.4	Mean Annual Infiltration Rate of the Soil (HAD)	Germany	BfG	2013	Raster	1:25,000	X	X	FAI
2.3.5	Soil water balance in Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m	X		FAIR
2.3.6	Calculated daily, monthly and average monthly values for different characteristic elements of soil and crops	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Point	-		X	IR
2.3.7	Daily grids of soil temperature at 5 cm depth	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Raster	1 km		X	IR
2.3.8	Daily grids of soil moisture under grass and sandy loam	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Raster	1 km		X	IR
2.3.9	Derived soil property maps – Hydrology Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m			
2.3.10	Soil-hydrological map Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2017	Raster	100 m	X		FAI
2.3.11	Pedological moisture level Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2017	Raster	50 m	X		FAI
2.3.12	Infiltration water rate Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2016	Polygon	1:25,000	X		FAIR
2.3.13	Derived hydrological parameter for agricultural areas (BFD5L), Hesse & Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-HE, DE-RP	HLNUG & LGB	2017	Polygon	1:5,000	X	X	FAIR
2.3.14	Groundwater depth isolines Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2016	Line	1:200,000	X	X	FAI
2.3.15	Soil-hydrological maps Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000	X		FAR
2.3.16	Derived maps based on the soil map BK50, Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2018	Polygon	1:50,000	X		FAIR
2.3.17	Derived soil hydrological maps based on the IS BK 50, North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.3.18	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200) in Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.3.19	Derived hydrological maps (BÜK200), Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2002	Polygon	1:200,000	X		FAI
2.3.20	Soil-hydrological maps (BÜK100) for the Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000	X		FA
2.3.21	Soil-hydrological maps for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2007	Polygon	1:200,000	X		FAI
2.3.22	Derived soil-hydrological maps based on German soil taxation for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2012	Polygon	1:10,000	X		FAI
2.4 Soil map products – Soil Erosion									
2.4.1	Soil erosion risk assessment in Europe data (MESALES model)	Europe	JRC	2002	Raster	1:1,000,000		X	FAR
2.4.2	Soil erodibility (K- Factor) - high resolution dataset for Europe	EU25	JRC	2014	Raster	500 m		X	FAR
2.4.3	Soil Erosion by Water (RUSLE2015)	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster	100 m		X	FAR
2.4.4	Net erosion and sediment transport in Europe using WaTEM/SEDEM	EU28	JRC	2018	Raster	100 m		X	FAR
2.4.5	Cover management factor (C-factor) for the EU - LANDUM	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster/ Polygon	100 m		X	FAR

	model								
2.4.6	Soil risks in Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m	X		FAIR
2.4.7	Potential soil erosion risk through water on arable soils in Germany	Germany	BGR	2014	Raster	250 m/ 1:1,000,000	X	X	FAIR
2.4.8	Potential risk of wind erosion on arable soils in Germany	Germany	BGR	2014	Raster	250 m/ 1:1,000,000	X	X	FAIR
2.4.9	Soil erosion risk through water for Germany	Germany	UBA	2011	Raster	1 km			-
2.4.10	Soil erosion risk through wind for Germany	Germany	UBA	2017	Raster	1 km			-
2.4.11	Soil erosion in Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m	X		FAI
2.4.12	Soil erosion risk for soils in Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1:300,000		X	FAIR
2.4.13	Erodibility of the topsoil in North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.4.14	Potential erosion risk of the arable land, Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LBG	2017	Polygon	1:5,000	X	X	FAIR
2.4.15	Water erosion risk for agricultural areas (CCW SL WMS), Saarland	DE-SL	LVGL-SL	2018	Polygon	1:100,000	X		FA
2.4.16	Map of erosion risk for Saxonian soils	DE-SN	LfULG	2013	Polygon	1:50,000		X	FAIR
2.5 Soil map products – Soil Carbon and Organic Matter Content									
2.5.1	Global Soil Organic Carbon Map (GSOCmap)	Global	FAO	2017	Raster	1 km		X	FAIR
2.5.2	Soil Organic Carbon - Saturation capacity in Europe	EU28	JRC	2016	Raster	250 m		X	FAR
2.5.3	CENTURY – pan-European baseline for SOC	Europe	JRC	2014	Polygon	-		X	FAR
2.5.4	Variations in topsoil organic carbon content across Europe	Europe	JRC/ EEA	2010	Raster (Image)	1 km		X	FA
2.5.5	Predicted distribution of SOC content in Europe (SoilTrEC project)	EU28	JRC	2016	Raster/ Point	1 km		X	FAR
2.5.6	Organic matter content of topsoils	Germany	BGR	2007	Polygon	1:1,000,000		X	FAIR
2.5.7	Organic carbon in the soils of Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	50 m	X		FAI
2.5.8	C _{org} -content in the soil of Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1:300,000		X	FAIR
2.5.9	Carbon content of the subsoil in Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2014	Polygon	1:50,000	X		FAIR
2.6 Soil map products – Input and Flow of Nutrients and Substances									
2.6.1	Global assessment of soil phosphorus retention potential	Global	Batjes, N. H.	2016	Raster	30"		X	FAIR
2.6.2	DayCent model - N ₂ O emissions from agricultural soils in Europe	Europe	JRC	2017	Point/ Raster	1 km		X	FAR
2.6.3	Maps of the Storing and Filtering Capacity of the Soils in Europe	EU27	JRC	2015	Polygon/ Raster	1:1,000,000 1 km		X	FAR
2.6.4	Soil substances in Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m	X		FAIR
2.6.5	Nitrogen and sulphur deposition for Germany (PINETI-model)	Germany	UBA	2017	Raster	250 m		X	FAR
2.6.6	Relative binding strength for heavy metals of soils in Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1:300,000		X	FAIR
2.6.7	Potential risk for nitrate leaching on arable areas in Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000	X		FAIR
2.6.8	Derived maps based on the soil	DE-NI	LBEG	2018	Polygon	1:50,000	X		FAIR

	map BK50 Lower Saxony								
2.6.9	Denitrification potential of the soil (BÜK50) for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2015	Polygon	1:50,000	X		FAIR
2.6.10	Denitrification potential of the soil (IS BK 50), North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.6.11	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200) in Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.6.12	Nitrate retention capacity (BÜK200), Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2002	Polygon	1:200,000	X		FAI
2.6.13	Nitrate retention capacity, Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000	X		FA
2.6.14	Background values of the topsoil, Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2014	Polygon	1:200,000		X	FAIR
2.7 Soil map products – Soil Management and Soil Functional Datasets									
2.7.1	Agricultural Census 2010	EU28	JRC/ Destatis	2017	(Polygon)	NUTS2/ NUTS3			F
2.7.2	Farm Structure Survey 2016	EU28	JRC/ Destatis	2018	(Polygon)	NUTS2/ NUTS3			F
2.7.3	Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas	EU27	JRC	2016	Raster	1 km		X	FAR
2.7.4	European map of soil suitability to provide a platform for most human activities	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster	1 km		X	FAR
2.7.5	Soil quality rating for cropland in Germany	Germany	BGR/ ZALF	2013	Polygon	1:1,000,000		X	FAIR
2.7.6	Soil capability in Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m	X	X	FAIR
2.7.7	Soil depth (rooting depth) in Germany	Germany	BGR	2015	Raster	250 m	X	X	FAIR
2.7.8	Sensitivity of soils to soil compaction	Germany	BGR	2015	Raster	250 m		X	FAIR
2.7.9	Derived soil property maps and soil function maps for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m	X		FA
2.7.10	Soil function maps for selected regions in Bavaria	DE-BY	Lfu-BY	2017	Polygon	1:25,000	X		FAIR
2.7.11	Areal soil data for agricultural areas (BFD5L) in Hesse & Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-HE, DE-RP	HLNUG & LGB	2017	Polygon	1:5,000	X	X	FAIR
2.7.12	Soil function assessment map for Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000			FAI
2.7.13	Derived products based on the soil map BK50, Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2017	Polygon	1:50,000	X		FAIR
2.7.14	Derived soil function maps based on the IS BK 50, North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.7.15	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200), Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAI
2.7.16	Soil function maps (BÜK100), Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000	X		FA
2.7.17	Derived maps for soil functions and protection, Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2015	Polygon	1:50,000	X	X	FAIR

* reduced data version is freely available

1. Soil sample and survey data

Measured soil data for the state area of Germany are provided by international, European and national institutions, while the first are based on the latter. At the international level there are a lot of activities ongoing, especially for soil profile data, to harmonize and integrate them, mainly linked by the ISRIC – World Soil Information which hosts the World Data Centre for Soils.

For pan-European harmonized data the first address is the European Soil Database of the [European Soil Data Centre \(ESDAC\)](#). Here, the most important survey program for topsoil data is the periodic Land Use/land Cover Area frame Survey LUCAS for sampling soil properties in 25 European countries since 2009.

1.1 Topsoil and surface data

1.1.1	International Soil Moisture Network - Datasets	International	ISMN	-	Point	5'
Description	The International Soil Moisture Network is a data hosting facility and international cooperation network for in-situ soil moisture data. It is coordinated by the Global Energy and Water Exchanges Project (GEWEX) in cooperation with the Group of Earth Observation (GEO), the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS), the European Space Agency, TU Wien and the Rutgers University. The ISMN is operated in cooperation with the Global Soil Moisture Databank of the Rutgers University.					
Completeness	For Russia a comparatively dense and widespread network of stations is recorded in the database with data starting in the 1950th. For Germany only four station networks in DE-NW, DE-BB and DE-BY are recorded: TERENO, COSMO, UDC-SMOS and MOL-RAO (DWD Lindenberg). For spatially and temporally consistent data about soil moisture in Germany use the database of the DWD-Climate Data Center .					
Access	http://www.geo.tuwien.ac.at/insitu/data_viewer/ISMN.php The data are presented via a map application where the data hosting network institution is displayed. A click on the point in the map opens an information box with metadata (station name, network name, network URL, time frame of data availability, variables measured, soil moisture depth measured, used soil moisture sensors). A link provides the data in form of an interactive graph where three variables can be selected for presentation but not for download. The presentation of the displayed station points can be filtered by continent, time frame (starting at the latest 1950 till present year) and area (geo-location box). For data download, a registration is required.					

1.1.2	FLUXNET – network of eddy covariance sites	International	U.S. Dep. of Energy	2007/2015	Point	-
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Description FLUXNET is a global activity for the measurement of fluxes of different Green House Gases measured mainly using the eddy covariance technique. It is collaborated and participated voluntarily by local Tower Teams and Regional Networks (e.g. the European Eddy Fluxes Database) and includes more than 800 active and historic flux measurement sites. The FLUXNET-Fluxdata website is hosted at the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (USA). The flux measurement sites are linked across a confederation of regional networks in North, Central and South America, Europe, Asia, Africa, and Australia. The most recent dataset produced is the FLUXNET2015 Dataset (<http://fluxnet.fluxdata.org//data/fluxnet2015-dataset/>), which includes over 1,500 site-years of data from 212 sites (15 sites in Germany). The previous dataset was produced in 2007 (La Thuile Dataset), containing over 960 site-years of data from 252 sites (<http://fluxnet.fluxdata.org//data/la-thuile-dataset/>).

Access There are two main FLUXNET portals: the FLUXNET-ORNL website (<https://fluxnet.ornl.gov/>), that maintains the catalog of all the existing and past eddy covariance sites globally, giving access to historical collection such the Marconi dataset and providing useful tools such updated images, MODIS cutout, and references. The second portal is the FLUXNET-Fluxdata website (<https://fluxnet.fluxdata.org/>) providing access to the regional flux networks datasets as well as the ORNL DAAC (https://daac.ornl.gov/cgi-bin/dataset_lister.pl?p=9). The FLUXNET2015 Dataset is distributed in files separated by sites, by temporal aggregation resolutions (e.g., half-hourly or yearly) and by data products (e.g., SUBSET or FULLSET). The metadata are also documented in the catalogue EARTHDATA (<https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/portal/ornl/daac/>).

1.1.3	ICOS Carbon Portal - Datasets	Europe	ICOS	2015	point	-
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Description ICOS Carbon Portal is the data portal of the Integrated Carbon Observation System established by the European Research Infrastructure Consortium. It provides observational data from the state of the carbon cycle in Europe and the world. The Carbon Portal is the data centre of the ICOS infrastructure. ICOS will collect greenhouse gas concentration and fluxes observations from three separate networks.

Validity All measurement data available in the Carbon Portal are quality controlled through the ICOS thematic centres: Ecosystem, Atmospheric and Ocean Thematic Centres and a Central Analytical laboratory.

Access The data usage is free of charge under CC BY 4.0 at <https://www.icos-cp.eu/>.

1.1.4	LUCAS topsoil survey 2009	Europe	JRC	2013	Point	-
Description	<p>In 2009 the European Commission launched a soil assessment component to the periodic Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) which is carried out by EUROSTAT since 2001. The scope was to create a harmonised and comparable topsoil assessment for Europe. Soil samples from 0-20-cm depth were taken in order to analyze physical and chemical parameters of topsoil. The georeferenced points (GPS latitude and longitude in decimal degrees) are a sub-sample of a regular 2 x 2 km grid (10% of the points). The 2009 LUCAS campaign addressed multispectral reflectance data and the following soil properties: clay, silt and sand content, coarse fragments, pH, organic carbon content, CaCO₃, total nitrogen, soluble phosphorus, potassium, cation exchange capacity, heavy metal content and exchangeable acidity. For the LUCAS topsoil survey in 2009 19,969 soil samples were collected in the EU25 (except Bulgaria and Rumania) under standardised sampling procedure (Tóth et al., 2013a). In Germany soil samples from about 2850 sites were recorded.</p>					
Currentness	<p>The LUCAS 2018 survey has start in March 2018 and its results, as well as the results from the LUCAS 2015 survey, are expected to be released in 2019. This survey will include for the first time: bulk density, soil biodiversity, visual assessment of soil erosion and thickness of the organic horizon in organic-rich soils.</p>					
Validity	<p>The number of selected soil sample points is proportional to the percentage of land use coverage for each country. Due to the availability of forest soil data (BIOSOIL project), 1/3 of the forest points were reduced in favour for arable site and grassland site points (Tóth et al., 2013a).</p>					
Access	<p>The LUCAS database is stored in the ESDAC and can be ordered free of charge with an online request form. The soil properties data are in MS Excel format (LUCAS_TOPSOIL_v1.xlsx) and the soil multispectral data are in the formats RDATA (LUCAS_TOPSOIL_v1_spectral.rdata) and CSV (LUCAS_TOPSOIL_spectral.csv). Some of the topsoil physical properties were modelled for GIS maps in a resolution of 500 m (Ballabio C., Panagos P., Montanarella L. 2016). Based on the original point data a package with a number of corresponding shapefiles was created in 2018 (SoilAttr_LUCAS2009).</p>					

1.1.5	German weather station data – soil temperature	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Point	-
Description	<p>The historical data recorded from 1949 are quality controlled measurements and observations derived from DWD stations and legally and qualitatively equivalent partner stations operated for climatological and climate related applications (ftp://ftp-cdc.dwd.de/pub/CDC/observations_germany/climate/). The observations are zipped together with comprehensive station metadata (station relocation, instrument change, time zones, change of algorithms) as txt-files and html-files. The data are available per station, for 470 stations in Germany. Measured values are (beside other parameters) available for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hourly soil temperature (in 2 cm, 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, 100 cm depth) • Daily soil temperature (in 2 cm, 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm, 50 cm, 100 cm depth) 					

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily precipitation height [mm] and form • Hourly precipitation height [mm] and form
Interoperability	The metadata are so far neither machine-readable nor available via API.
Completeness	The start and end of the observation period at the individual station is very different, some of the stations have a short observation time or stopped their observation long time ago. The resolution of the observation net is therefore perhaps spatially incomplete in the temporal dimension.
Currentness	The data in the sub-directories /historical/ are provided in annual intervals. The most recent datasets (present day) are stored in the sub-directory /recent/ (without quality check so far).
Access	The data are available free of charge with consideration of the rights of use via the FTP-Server of the DWD Climate Data Center (CDC) (ftp://ftp-cdc.dwd.de/pub/CDC/observations_germany/). It has to be considered, that the assigned metadata of the stations are only in German. The information about the geographical position of the station is more precise in the station list [EB_Stundenwerte_Beschreibung_Stationen.txt]. The R-Package <i>rdwd</i> (Boessenkool, 2017) provides a tool for automatically download and visualization of large dataset of the Climate Data Center.

1.1.6	TERENO - TERrestrial ENvironmental Observatories	Sites in Germany	FZ Jülich	2008	Point	-
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Description	<p>TERENO, an initiative under the roof of the Helmholtz Association, aims to establish an observation platform that connects various terrestrial observatories in different regions in Germany. The program started in 2008 with three observatories and manages now four TERENO-project observatory sites: Eifel/ Lower Rhine Valley Observatory, Bavarian Alps/ pre-Alps Observatory, German-Lowland Observatory, Harz/ Central German Lowland Observatory.</p> <p>The “TERENO Data Discovery Portal” provides access to research data of the four TERENO-project observatory sites. The data portal is also connected to data from third parties.</p> <p>TERENO includes observation data about soil moisture, soil humidity, soil water content, soil temperature, cosmic ray, global radiation, longwave radiation, shortwave radiation, albedo, lysimetric data (percolation water, evaporation), data of an eddy covariance station, emission data, fluorescence spectrometer data, flux meter data, groundwater, percolation, precipitation, air temperature, air pressure, relative humidity.</p>
Access	<p>http://teodoor.icg.kfa-juelich.de/ibg3searchportal2/index.jsp</p> <p>The search interface allows a search by temporal, spatial and thematic filters, but only for data, which were observed by the Eifel-Ruhr and/or the German-Lowland Observatories. Online applications displaying data from three different weather radar stations or automated interpolated soil water content data (SoilNet). “Manuscripts using data from the TERENO should be sent to the data owners and to the TERENO coordination team for review.”</p>

1.1.7	Edaphobase	Germany	SGN	-	Point	-
Description	Edaphobase is a project of the Senckenberg Society for the collection and publication of information from literature and museum collections on the distribution and ecology of soil invertebrates (earthworms, small earthworms, nematodes, springtails, moss/ beetle mites, gamasina mites, centipedes, millipedes, and woodlice). The information system is part of the existing GBIF data structure and as a project sponsor within the framework of GBIF-Germany connected to other museums and collections in Germany. Edaphobase is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (grant number 01LI0901A and 01LI1301A). All individuals of a species found at a site of sampling (plot) in a defined stratum (e.g., litter, Ah 0-5 cm) at a sampling date form a dataset in Edaphobase. In addition, there are entities that are not directly related to the record, but are linked to it by metadata (person, source, publisher, copy, synonym).					
Completeness	The database has a spatial focus on Germany and neighbouring countries but hosts also data from other countries and continents collected by the partner museums.					
Supplement	A user handbook is available online (in German).					
Access	https://portal.edaphobase.org/ The data are accessible in web application with filter facilities and spatial search. To use all functions of the map and for data export (except raw data), a registration is required. Without registration the data plots can be localized and identified. For the access to the raw data a legitimate interest must be proven.					

1.1.8	Exploratories for Biodiversity - Datasets	Sites in Germany	Friedrich Schiller University Jena	2008	Point	-
Description	The Biodiversity Exploratories were installed in 2006 in the frame of a German Science Foundation funded research project at three exemplary large-scale and long-term research sites. The objective of the project was to enhance the understanding of the relationship between biodiversity of different taxa and levels, between biodiversity and land use and the role of biodiversity and ecosystem processes. In the research data infrastructure Biodiversity Exploratories Information System (BExIS) 132 datasets of below ground samples are available for public, including samples of fungi and microalgae or microarthropods. BExIS is not directly linked with Edaphobase.					
Reusability	The BExIS provides a detailed metadata template for its datasets. Unfortunately, this template was often not completed by the data owner/ producer and important information to interpret the data is often missing.					
Access	The project maintains for its data the BExIS (https://www.bexis.uni-jena.de/) but provides no universal identifier like a DOI. At the BExIS the data and metadata are provided with free access. Some of the datasets are also registered in the data infrastructure of GBIF where they are published with a DOI (e.g. Species Soil Macrofauna 2008 DOI: 10.15468/frzwp).					

1.2 Soil Profile Data

1.2.1 International and national level

At the international level there exist soil profile data infrastructures and databases, e.g. the WoSIS Soil Profile Database managed by ISRIC – World Soil Information and the Soil Profile Analytical Database of Europe (SPADBE) within the European Soil Database. For both, the data access is without restrictions but the spatial coverage is sparse (in the case of WoSIS only 50 profiles for Germany).

The soil profile data bases of the federal Geological Surveys and the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (Members of the AG Boden) which recorded the data in the frame of special survey programs and projects are the largest data sources for soil profile data in Germany. Other programs at the national level are the National Forest Soil Survey and the German Agricultural Soil Inventory which were executed by the Thünen Institute. The access to datasets is generally not free and is a subject of individual agreements.

1.2.1	WoSIS Soil Profile Database	International	ISRIC	2016	Point	-
Description	The World Soil Information Service (WoSIS) contains the data of about 120,000 soil profiles from all over the world and is part of the ISRIC World Data centre for Soils Data Repository. For Germany there are 50 soil profile recorded in the database (2016-07). The data are also presented and accessible via SoilGrids.org. The dataset includes: Bulk density fine earth (kg/dm ³); Bulk density whole soil (kg/dm ³); Calcium carbonate equivalent (g/kg in the fine earth fraction < 2 mm) also known as inorganic carbon; Cation exchange capacity (CEC) cmol c/kg; Clay total (g/100g); Coarse fragments gravimetric total (g/100g); Coarse fragments volumetric total (cm ³ /100cm ³); Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC, cmol c/kg); Electrical conductivity (ECx, mS/m); Organic carbon (g/kg); pH CaCl ₂ ; pH H ₂ O; pH KCl; pH NaF; Sand total (g/100g); Silt total (g/100g); Soil classification FAO; Soil classification (national/local); USDA Soil Taxonomy; Soil classification WRB (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015); Total carbon (g/kg); Water retention gravimetric (g/100g); Water retention volumetric (cm ³ /100cm ³). The database includes also the regional SOTER maps.					
Validity	All data submitted for consideration by the data providers in WoSIS are first preserved 'as is' (level A) in the ISRIC WDC-Soils Data Repository. Subsequently, they are quality-assessed (level B), standardised (preferably done by the data provider) and, where possible, harmonised (level C). Generally, the comparability and standardization of the profiles data has limitations (Ribeiro et al., 2015; Batjes et al., 2017; ISRIC, 2018).					
Access	The WoSIS datasets are distributed in two formats. The most recent, latest (dynamic) version can be accessed through an OGC-compliant WFS (http://data.isric.org/geoserver/wosis_latest/wfs). Further, snapshot (static) dataset in TXT format (about 670 MB) are provided for consistent citation purposes ftp://public:public@ftp.isric.org/wosis_snapshot/WoSIS_2016_July.zip (http://www.isric.org/explore/wosis/accessing-wosis-derived-datasets). Since early 2018 the complement of soil properties considered in 'wosis_latest' differs from the static version.					

1.2.2	European Soil Database v2.0 – Soil Profile Analytical Database	Europe, Eurasia	JRC	2004	Point	-
Description	<p>The Soil Profile Analytical Database of Europe (SPADBE), version 2.1.0.0 is part of the European Soil Database and supplements there the derived qualitative soil property information of the Soil Geographical Database with quantitative data. The database includes two types of profiles to a depth of 2 metres: estimated profiles (representative for specific Soil Typological Units) and measured profiles. For different soil horizons the following attributes are included: texture with particle size groups, organic matter content (C, N), structure, total N, pH, Exchangeable Sodium Percentage or Sodium Adsorption ratio, CaCO₃ content, CaSO₄ content, electric conductivity, cation exchange capacity and exchangeable bases, soil water retention, bulk density, root depth groundwater level, parent material. The attributes are given per horizon.</p> <p>For Germany there are 19 measured profile descriptions available, including 12 profiles on agricultural sites.</p>					
Resolution	The profile coordinates are given in degrees and minutes so the resolution is reduced.					
Completeness	There are missing values in some profiles single parameters.					
Validity	The estimated profile data have been estimated by experts. At present there is no quantified standard procedure to prove the accuracy or precision of the data and the responsibility for accuracy remains with the contributing institutions.					
Supplement	<p>For details about the analytical procedures see European Soil Database v2. Instructions Guide. https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ESDB_Archive/ESDBv2/esdb/sgdbe/metadata/InstructionsGuide.doc</p> <p>Metadata of SPADBE: https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ESDB_Archive/ESDBv2/popup/sp_meta.htm</p> <p>Breuning-Madsen, H. and Jones, R.J.A., 1995. Soil profile analytical database for the European Union. Danish Journal of Geography, 95, 49-57. https://doi.org/10.1080/00167223.1995.10649363</p>					
Access	The access is provided free of charge via the ESDAC but must be requested with an online request form. The estimated profiles are provided in DBF-format and the measured profile data in EXCEL-format.					

1.2.3	Laboratory and Profile Database BGR	Germany	BGR	-	Point	-
Description	<p>The laboratory and profile database is one part of BGR soil information system (FISBo BGR), accompanied by the methodological database and the map and geo databases (<i>Flächendatenbanken</i>). Here, profile data and analysis results of the BGR projects are stored and managed. This includes single variables for the whole profile as well as variables per horizon. The oldest dataset originates from the year 1934.</p>					
Completeness	For each value in the database the coded information about the sampling, sample preparation, used analysis method or technique is recorded.					
Validity	For quality assurance, several check routines (e.g. horizon comparisons, comparisons of laboratory results with observations in the field) are integrated in the database.					
Access	The database is intended for internal purposes. The database holds data from					

various sources, including projects from the federal states or other federal institutions. For this reason, the data is subject to different levels of protection (e.g., protected data without right of use or data with limited right of use). On request, partial information from the database is available. https://www.bgr.bund.de/DE/Themen/Boden/Informationsgrundlagen/Bodenkundliche_Karten_Datenbanken/labor_profildatenbank.html?nn=1541164

1.2.4	German Agricultural Soil Inventory (BZE-LW)	Germany	TI	2018	Point	8 km
Description	<p>The national monitoring program “Bodenzustandserhebung Landwirtschaft – BZE-LW” (04/2008 – 12/2018) was implemented by the Thünen Institute to detect the soil carbon and nitrogen content and the soil texture in the top 100 cm soil layer including only agricultural areas, meadows, gardens and special crops. It is the first nationwide, consistent and representative monitoring program of soil organic carbon stock in agricultural soils. 3104 sample points in Germany, selected by an 8 km x 8 km grid of sample points, were sampled and adjusted by control of representativeness. The sampling method (profile description and sampling points in a 10 m radius around) is in accordance with the German National Forest Soil Survey (<i>Bodenzustandserhebung Wald I + II</i>). Compared to other European soil monitoring programs, this soil inventory is the only one which surveys soil management and farming practices for the past 10 years. The sample collection was finished at the end of 2017. All data were collected in accordance with the German Soil Survey Guideline, 5th Ed. (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005).</p> <p>Goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation of the current carbon stock at agricultural areas • Analysis of the interdependencies of organic carbon content and climate, land use, soil management and soil characteristics (Bach et al., 2011) • Model building for prediction of the carbon stock development under conditions of climate change (Bach et al., 2011) • Spatial precision of the sample points is 1 km (maybe problematic for large scale modelling) • Parameter: TOC, TIC, total N, soil type, pH, electrical conductivity (H₂O), texture (fine and coarse), dry bulk density, root mass, total N, recent and past soil management and farm structure, crop rotation, catch crops 					
Currentness	<p>The data collected from the soil profiles will be linked with the main soil association from the soil survey map 1: 1.000.000 (BÜK1000) in cooperation with the BGR.</p>					
Access	<p>The results will be passed on to cooperation partners with a justified interest. The data collection on the farm structure and management will not be accessible due to privacy issues (Contact: Roland Prietz (field survey), Anna Jacobs (Analysis), Arne Heidkamp (laboratory), Axel Don (Modelling)). A comprehensive report with the first analysis results was published in PFD and printed version (Jacobs et al., 2018).</p>					

1.2.2 Soil profile data in German Federal States

The central address for quality approved and nation-wide consistent soil profile data is the soil profile data base of the BGR and the dominant soil profiles (*Leitbodenprofile*) of the BÜK200. The content of the data base are products of the BGR surveys or were provided by the state offices (see members of the AG Boden). The federal states' offices survey soils, their composition, properties and distribution by collecting soil profile data in accordance with the mandate formulated in the German Federal Soil Protection Act (BBodSchG, 1998) and the Soil Protection Acts of the Federal States. The profiles' recording is generally embedded in long-term survey programs in the frame of the [Bodenkundliche Landesaufnahme](#) like the German soil taxation ([Bodenschätzung](#)), the long-term soil survey and the [Forstliche Standortskartierung](#). These programs differ in their observation methodology and soil description standards and are not comparable without background information. The data pool was (and is) steadily transferred into the KA4- (AG Boden, 1994) or KA5-standard (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) but the state offices differ in their status of completion. Due to that fact, the state offices generally provide these data only after consultation and detailed statements about the aim of the data user.

In the federal states at the area of the former GDR, there was a profile database established in 1960 till 1990 by the Research Center for Soil Fertility (FZB) according to the nomenclature of the GDR. After 1990, the data were edited and transferred in the database of the BGR and the new established databases of the federal states.

1.2.5	Soil profile data Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	-	-	-
Description	The soil profile monitoring is operated by the State Office for Geology, Resources and Mining (LGRB). The data are managed in a geo-scientific information system (FIS BODEN) storing more than 75,000 borings and laboratory analysis including about 250 sample profiles.					
Currentness	Most of the soil profile descriptions are based on the KA3 standard and are so far not translated (AG Bodenkunde, 1982).					
Reusability	There is only very sparse information published by the state office about the structure and management of the information system and the soil data (LGRB, 1999).					
Access	The soil profile data are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the LUBW. The sample profiles (<i>Musterprofile</i>) of the 55 BK25 map sheets are offered in the LGRB-Shop in ASCII-format (10,-€ per map sheet). Information about the current state of the database is not available online but on request.					

1.2.6	Soil profile data Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2018	-	-
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Description	In Bavaria 34,350 soil profiles from different projects (e.g. pedological land survey) are documented and stored in the database <i>Bodeninformationssystem Bayern</i> (BIS-BY) managed by the Bavarian State Office for Environment (correspondence with LfU-BY, 2018-05-21) and presented in an online web map application. The documentation starts in the 1950s. The LfU provides information about the pedological field survey online (LfU-BY, 2018) and in a comprehensive report (Bayerisches Geologisches Landesamt, 2005).
Currentness	The soil profiles are described in accordance with the KA5 (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005), supplemented by physical and chemical analysis in the laboratory.
Access	Information, data and map services are provided for public users at the 'UmweltAtlas Bayern – Boden' (http://www.umweltatlas.bayern.de/). The user receives detailed information (e.g. humus content and texture per horizon) about each profile and can request selected data for download.

1.2.7	Soil profile data for Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	-	-	-
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Description	The State Office for Mining, Geology and Resources (LBGR) maintains an information system for soil geology. This system contains about 6,000 profile data recorded by the LBGR, about 6,300 datasets from external sources and more than 100,000 legacies or historical datasets (e.g. PRODAT, melioration projects, German soil taxation - 'Bodenschätzung').
Completeness	All these soil profile data are distributed very unevenly over the area of Brandenburg. The LBGR data and external data are in accordance with KA5 standard (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005), while the legacy datasets are stored in their original format (TGL 24300 and other specific standards).
Access	Due to very different release rights, processing states, quality control and validation with laboratory data, the LBGR profile data is generally not accessible for external users. For external users, the archive of area related soil forms (<i>Flächenbodenformenarchiv</i>) is offered, which is based on a statistical evaluation of the LBGR data (Bauriegel, 2005). Available without restrictions are the description and location of the soil profiles of the German soil taxation framework (Bodenschätzung) in WMS (http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bograbloecher_wms?) and WFS (http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bograbloecher_wfs?).

1.2.8	Soil profile data for Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	-	-	-
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Description	The <i>Bodenzustandskataster</i> of the State Office for Nature protection, Environment and Geology (HLNUG) is one part of the <i>Bodenformenarchiv</i> (BoFA) and merges all point-related soil data (soil description and laboratory analysis) in a cadaster according to the soil protection standard Hessen (Friedrich et al., 2003). The data are managed in the database system BOFA.
Resolution	The spatial precision of the profiles' location is 1 km.
Access	The data are available for scientific use within projects funded by German Ministries. The web map application Bodenviewer Hessen provides profile descriptions in PDF format (http://bodenviewer.hessen.de/mapapps/resources/apps/bodenviewer/index.htm?lang=de). An extern version of the data base application "BOFA-extern" was updated in early 2018 and will be available after request from late 2018.

1.2.9	Soil profile data for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	-	-	-
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Description In Lower Saxony the State Agency for Mining, Energy and Geology (LBEG) monitored within 40 years about 30,000 soil profiles.

Currentness The profile monitoring and description is based on different standards - KA4 and KA5 (AG Boden, 1994; Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005).

Access Data are available via specific server ports in different formats on request and as a subject to agreement with the LBEG under consideration of farmers' privacy. Descriptions of the soil profiles, the spatial position and an image of the horizon sequence are visualized in the NIBIS map server.
<http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/?TH=611>

1.2.10	Soil profile for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	-	-	-
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Description Point and area data on the distribution and characteristics of the soils of the state of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern are managed by the information system *FIS Boden* (FISBO-MV) maintained by the the State Office for Nature conservation, Environment and Geology (LUNG). The FISBO includes data of the moor plot catalogue, soil profile data base (incl. long-term soil monitoring) and laboratory data base. It was supplemented by digital versions of the MMK, the soil appraisal data („Bodenschätzung“) and the site assessments of melioration activities.

Currentness Most of the profile information is converted into KA5-standard (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005).

Access The data are provided only on request and by consultation of the respective contact person at the LUNG.

1.2.11	Soil profile data for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	LANUV	2016	-	-
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Description The Information System on Soil Contamination (*Fachinformationssystem Stoffliche Bodenbelastung* - FIS StoBo) stores data about the contamination of soils in North Rhine-Westphalia and is managed by the State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer protection (LANUV). It currently comprises approx. 75,000 sample data from approx. 60,000 locations with point-related information on toxicologically relevant heavy metals and persistent organic substances and compounds.

Reusability The soil profile descriptions were recorded in accordance with the KA4 standard (AG Boden, 1994), supplemented and edited by the own survey guidelines and data keys (Dworschak et al., 1998; Dworschak et al., 1999).

Access The online web map application of the FIS StoBo (www.stobo.nrw.de) provides also basic soil properties per observation point like pH-value, sand, clay and silt content, C_{org} and cation exchange capacity. The data reports can be downloaded per point in PDF-format or in CSV-format for several points.

The Geological Survey (GD-NW) provides soil profile descriptions (soil type and soil structure per horizon, humus, CaCO₃, pH, cation exchange capacity, base saturation, as part of the Information System of the soil map 1:5,000 (IS BK 5) in PDF-format, but with restricted access (see record [2.1.15](#) in this report).

1.2.12	Soil profile data for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	-	-	-
Description	<p>The State Office for Geology and Mining (LGB - Landesamt für Geologie und Bergbau, Ref. 93 – Landesbodenkunde) collects soil profile data in two categories of intensity since late 1980s: 1) borings in the field with standardized profile description; 2) sample profile ('Musterprofil') excavation with comprehensive description and soil sample analysis. So far the database stores data of about 180,000 soil explorations (information provided after request by the LGB, 2018-05-22).</p> <p>For the management of the pedological survey data the LGB uses the database BoFA (<i>Bodenformenarchiv</i>). It is the most important component of the soil information system (FISBO) and contains both the profile descriptions with the analysis data and the area data of the medium and large-scale map products (BFD 50, BFD 200). Within the scope of the project 'Bodenphysikalische Kennwerte – Auswertung der Bodenphysikdatenbank' of the LGB, parameters for water retention in soils are provided. The tables and graphs provide soil physical data based on KA5 (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) and WRB (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) standards. In addition, parameters for substrate-horizon groups are available (Dehner, 2018; Goldschmitt, 2018).</p>					
Validity	<p>The data are not quality approved and not based on the same standard even if the profiles are monitored today in accordance with the standards of the KA4/KA5 (AG Boden, 1994; Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The data key has changed 3-4 times since the 1980s.</p>					
Access	<p>Currently, there are data and descriptions for about 350 sample profiles freely available after request and about 350 sample profiles are in preparation.</p>					

1.2.13	Soil profile data for the Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	-	-	-
Description	<p>The Saarland Soil Information System SAARBIS consists of a soil profile database, a laboratory database and a method database. The profile database stores currently 8,250 profile datasets (information provided after request by the LUA, 2018-05-04). The oldest profile descriptions stored in SAARBIS were recorded in 1985 while most of the datasets of the Bodenkundliche Landesaufnahme originate from the years 1988-1995.</p>					
Currentness	<p>Most of the datasets in the database were converted in KA4-standard at the end of the 1990ies under consideration of regional characteristics.</p>					
Access	<p>The data access needs an official application form and a user agreement.</p>					

1.2.14	Soil profile data for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2018	-	-
Description	The Soil Information System (FIS) which is managed by the State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG) is part of the Environmental Information System Saxony (UIS) (LfULG, 2018a). There are currently approx. 62,000 master data records with over 226,000 horizon descriptions in the database (LfULG (ed.), 2018b). Furthermore, 2,093,000 individual analyzes of 67,900 soil samples are available.					
Validity	The PC-based program »UBODEN.net« is used for data acquisition and includes a plausibility check and a KA5-conformity check (LfULG, 2018a).					
Access	The dataset 'Bodenkundliche Aufschlüsse Sachsens' (LfULG, 2018c) presents soil profile data of the FIS-Boden for parts of the Saxony as WFS (https://geoportal.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services/boden/bka/MapServer/WFS/Server?) and is described by metadata (But: Data protection law, therefore only limited information). The dataset is also provided free of charge in SHAPE-format after request via the download service (https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/boden/27787.htm). The interactive map contains basic information (location, substrate type, soil type) of the respective soil profiles and is also presented in the web map application iDA (https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/infosysteme/ida/). More detailed information can be provided on request and under recognition of the data protection from the FIS-Boden. Data export is realized in Excel/CSV and html.					

1.2.15	Soil profile data for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	-	-	-
Description	The states' soil monitoring is operated by the State Office for Geology and Mining (LAGB) which manages the data in the Soil Information System (FIS-Boden). The FIS-Boden includes the profile database SABO-P.					
Reusability	The result tables include detailed information about the analysis methods.					
Access	From the profile database information is provided only in individual cases. For the general description of soil forms the provision of profiles of the dominant soil type is offered (https://lagb.sachsen-anhalt.de/geologie/bodenkunde/fachinformationen-boden/fachinformationssystem-boden/). The soil parameters (soil type of the topsoil, water conductivity, potential cation exchange capacity, field capacity, usable field capacity and air capacity) of the German soil taxation are available as WMS and WFS converted in KA5-standard (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) via INSPIRE and Geoportal.de . WFS-URL: https://www.geodatenportal.sachsen-anhalt.de/gfds/ws/wfs/580c8e73-77e8-d023/GDI-LSA_LAGB_SCHAETZUNG_PARAMETER/ows.wfs?					

1.2.16	Soil profile data for Schleswig-Holstein	DE-SH	LLUR	-	-	-
Description	<p>The soil data management system FISBo is hosted by the State Office for Agriculture, Environment and rural areas (LLUR) which is developing also a special soil data information system 'Bodeninformationssystem' BODIS as a superior system (https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/Fachinhalte/B/boden/bodis.html). The profile database includes data from different projects like the pedological land survey, the soil threat cadastre and the long-term soil monitoring as well as data for specific reports and assessment projects. In the frame of the pedological land survey more than 200,000 soil profiles were described, but only 25 % are stored in digital formats so far. These profiles include 1,300 dominant soil type profiles which are described by different parameters depending on specific soil type questions. Further, about 56,000 profile data of the German soil taxation (Bodenschätzung) are stored in the FISBo and are currently transferred in digital format (https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/Fachinhalte/B/boden/fachinformationssystemBoden.html)</p>					
Currentness	The historical profile descriptions are already transferred in modern nomenclature.					
Supplement	The LANU published a detailed report with descriptions of the observation programs and methods of the FISBo (LANU, 2007).					
Access	The data are only available after individual request.					

1.2.17	Soil profile data for Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	-	-	-
Description	<p>The State Institute for Environment and Geology (TLUG) stores soil profile information like the pedological land survey data and dominant soil type profile in a soil information system with digital point information.</p>					
Validity	<p>Currently, about 8,000 soil profile descriptions are recorded in accordance with the KA4 and KA5 (AG Boden, 1994; Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The validation process is not yet completed (correspondence with TLUG, 2018-05-15).</p>					
Access	<p>Soil monitoring data are generally only for internal use of the TLUG. Enquiries are reviewed and processed in case of individual agreements with the TLUG under consideration of farmers' privacy.</p>					

1.2.3 Long-term soil monitoring plots in German Federal States

The current status of Germany's soils and changing properties is continuously monitored in long-term soil monitoring plots (Boden-Dauerbeobachtungsflächen – BDF) on cropland, grassland, forestry soil and special-use soils (e.g. for human settlements and winegrowing). With the BDF chemical, physical and biological soil properties as well as land use are recorded and evaluated and gain insights into emerging trends (UBA, 2017a). The BDFs are distinguished in so called basic plots (Basis-BDF) to measure the characteristics of the soil solid phase and intensive plots (Intensiv-BDF) to describe the dynamic processes by measuring soil solution and deposition.

The data of the basic plots are transferred periodically to the German Environment Agency (UBA) which incorporates the data in a central national soil information system (bBIS). The rights of use remain by the concerning state offices. The UBA has the option to carry out assessments and scientific analysis of the data but under previous consultation of the state offices about the rights of use.

State Offices store results in specific soil information systems, so called 'Fachinformationssystemen Boden' or FISBo. The development of soil information systems was initiated by a proposal of the Conference of Environmental Ministers for the Federal States to implement standardized systems for all soil profile observation data. The BGR published a guideline for the development of such a system as a result of the coordination work of the federal Geological Surveys (BGR, 1996).

Since 2001, an action plan has been agreed on the basis of the "ad hoc AG" BDF of the Länderarbeitsgemeinschaft Boden (LABO) (Barth et al., 2000). This includes a framework for the investigation and for the parameter spectrum to be collected. However, there are no binding agreements on examination methods, data exchange and data consistency (Schilli et al., 2011). A study by the UBA which assessed the countrywide comparability of the data has found that there is no site at which all mandatory parameters specified by the LABO guidelines are measured. However, the standard parameter (grain sizes, raw density, pH, C and N contents, heavy metals) are covered in all states without major data gaps (Spatz, 2001).

1.2.18	Long-term soil monitoring Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LUBW	-	-	-
Description	The long-term soil monitoring has started 1986 with 155 plots and is operated by the State Office for Environment, Measurement and Nature Conservation (LUBW, formerly LfU-BW). 1992/1994 151 plots were analysed. In 2000 the number of plots was reduced to 33 plots (10 arable sites, 6 grassland sites and 17 forest sites) which are monitored at a 10-year interval. The first intensive plot was installed in 1995 and nowadays 5 plots are monitored.					
Access	The data are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the LUBW. The results are available in form of reports online (LfU-BW, 1992; LfU-BW, 1999; LUBW, 2008; LUBW, 2016).					

1.2.19	Long-term soil monitoring Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	-	-	-
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Description	For the 298 long-term soil monitoring plots three different authorities are responsible since 1985/86. The State Office for Environment (LfU) observes 61 basic monitoring plots at specific sites like stressed sites, nature conservation sites or water protection areas. At some of these sites the radioactivity is measured additionally. The State Office for Agriculture (LfL) leads the monitoring at 132 plots (93 arable areas, 27 grassland areas and 7 special crops). The State Office for Forest and Forestry (LWF) manages 78 plots. Some of these forest plots are supplemented by a forest climate station and detect also soil solution parameter and immission values beside the soil matrix parameter.
Access	The monitoring data of the primary survey and the first iteration are stored in an intern database of the State Office for Agriculture (LfL). The data are available for scientific use with consideration of privacy issues. The data transfer is managed by project-related agreements (LfL, IAB1a).

1.2.20	Long-term soil monitoring in Brandenburg	DE-BB	LfU-BB	2017	-	-
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Description	The soil monitoring is operated by the State Office for Environment (LfU), implemented since 1990 every 7-10 years, the latest was finished in 2016 on 23 arable plots, 7 grassland plots and 2 nature conservation plots. The LfU Brandenburg provides a list with short characteristics of each plot including spatial information (ETRS89) and information about soil type, soil texture, natural unit, parent material (LfU-BB, 2015). The measurement data are stored in the soil information system BoDIS (<i>Boden-Dauerbeobachtungs-Informationssystem-Brandenburg</i>). BoDIS is one part of the FIS BOS.
Access	The data are stored in the 'Fachinformationssystem Bodenschutz' FISBOS which includes the long-term soil monitoring database and a sample archive. The descriptive information of the BDF is freely available and provided in WFS (http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bdf_wfs?) and WMS (http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bdf_wms?language=ger&). The data and analysis results must be requested.

1.2.21	Long-term soil monitoring in Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	-	-	-
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Description	The HLNUG installed 67 long-term soil monitoring plots in 1992-1999 at representative agricultural and forest sites. The 66 basic plots and 1 intensive plot (airport Frankfurt/M.) are observed at intervals of 5 years (66 arable sites, 17 grassland sites, 22 forest sites and 2 sites with special crops).
Access	The web map application "BodenViewer Hessen" (http://bodenviewer.hessen.de/mapapps/resources/apps/bodenviewer/index.htm?lang=de) shows the locations of the long-term soil monitoring plots distinguished by land use type and profile descriptions in PDF format. The data are accessible for scientific use after request and an agreement of usage. The spatial precision of the profile locations is 1 km. An extern version of the data base application "BOFA-extern" which contains all data of the "Bodenzustandskataster Hessen" was updated in the first half of 2018 and will be available after request in the second half.

1.2.22	Long-term soil monitoring in Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2012/2015	-	-
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Description The LBEG conducts 90 long-term soil monitoring plots since 1991 (20 forest plots, 48 arable sites, 16 grassland sites, 5 near-natural site and 1 site in urban area). The measurements are implemented at an interval of 1-10 years depending on the parameter. The basic inventory of the plots is repeated in a 10-year interval. The monitoring frequency for microbial parameters is 1 to 3 years and 3 to 5 years for the parameters pH-value, organic carbon, plant-available nutrients and total N. The vegetation monitoring takes place every three years. The forest plots monitoring includes the annual (BDF-I) or 2-year (BDF-S) sampling of the leaves/needles for nutrition analysis and the observation of the crown defoliation. The basic inventory measurements include input/infiltration and output of substances by land use activities and deposition, chemical and non-chemical soil changes, analysis of vegetation and soil biology, percolation water and ground water. 19 plots are located on soils with specific threats (erosion, municipal waste, high farm manure input). At the intensive plots (BDF-I) on agricultural sites the percolation water is measured too combined with the monitoring of the nitrate/ammonium-concentration (Nmin) two or three times a year in a range of soil depths. For a special monitoring program, the heavy metal content is measured at 23 plots. The intensive plots at forest sites are supplemented by hydro-meteorological stations for observing the water balance. The data are supplemented by annual farm management parameters.

Access The reports published by the LBEG (Höper and Meesenburg, 2012; Kamermann et al., 2015) contain detailed information about the plots, the vegetation, percolation water, soil quality, erosion, deposition and the monitoring methods.

1.2.23	Long-term soil monitoring in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	-	-	-
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Description The long-term soil monitoring is operated by two different state offices: the plots on agricultural soils are surveyed since 1990 (30 plots in 2017 with 22 plots on arable areas, 7 on grassland sites and 1 in specific use - 16 agricultural plots more are planned) by the LUNG and the monitoring of forest soils is implemented since 1986 by the state forest administration on 57 plots (2016). The monitoring of the forest plots was operated 1986-89, 1991-95, 1999-2000 and later with an interval of 10 years.

Access The data are provided by the LUNG only on request.

1.2.24	Long-term soil monitoring in North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	LANUV	2005/2009	-	-
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Description The long-term soil monitoring is operated by the LANUV since 1992 at 20 plots. The concept for the plot selection intends the observation of the soil degradation factors like heavy metals and leaching of acidity on forest sites. The chemical parameters are monitored at a 10 yearly interval while the microbiological parameters are detected every 1 to 3 years.

Completeness The main intension for the monitoring is the detection of soil threats by the immission of heavy metals and leaching of acidity which causes a spatial concentration on forest areas. The concept does not provide a representative overview of the soil types in North Rhine-Westphalia. The LANUV is operating

further a monitoring program for humus content of arable soils since 2009. There are extensive and intensive monitoring plots. For 155 extensive plots under the Ap-horizon was surveyed once in 15 years. For 45 intensive plots the Ap-horizon and the subsoil up to 60 cm were surveyed regularly once a year (reduced parameter list) or every three years (complete parameter list).

Access Data of the long-term soil monitoring are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer protection under consideration of farmers' privacy. The State office provides analysis results, methods and plot descriptions in a detailed report for the observation period 1995-2007 (LANUV, 2005; Haag et al., 2009).

1.2.25	Long-term soil monitoring in Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	-	-	-
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Description The long-term soil monitoring plots were newly installed in 2009 at forest environmental control areas as part of the already implemented measurement net of the National Forest Soil Survey observed by the State Research Institute for Forest Ecology and Forestry (FAWF). The LGB observes in total 16 basic plots in low mountain ranges far from industrial emission sources.

Completeness Due to the late implementation of the long-term soil monitoring plots in 2009, the comparability with data of other German states is restricted. The soil monitoring includes so far only forest plots with low immissions from industrial areas.

Validity The methodological concept of the soil sample collection is based on Barth et al. (2000) which is also used in other German states. However, the concept is partly adjusted to the observation methods of the former installed forest soil condition inventory (BZE) which took place at the sites.

Access Data of the long-term soil monitoring are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the LGB. The sample collection methods and results are published in a detailed report (LGB, 2012).

1.2.26	Long-term soil monitoring in the Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2006	-	-
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Description The soil monitoring data are managed by the State Office for Environment Protection and Occupational Safety (LUA) with the soil information system SAARBIS. Today, the LUA observes 11 basic plots (5 arable area, 4 forest sites, 1 grassland, 1 special crop) including one plot for observations concerning soil erosion questions.

Access The plots are documented in a report with limited geospatial information (LUA, 2006). The geolocation information of 10 plots are available in the dataset of the BUEK100 ([2.1.16](#)).

1.2.27	Long-term soil monitoring in Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2015	-	-
Description	In Saxony the long-term soil monitoring was installed in 1993 by the State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG) which observes 57 basic plots (BDF I: 48 arable sites, 8 grassland, 1 fallow) and 5 intensive plots (BDF II) at sites with specific threatening factors (heavy metals, radionuclides, immission). The concept for the plot selection is determined by representativeness concerning soil communities, environmental units, geological units and land use. The measurements are repeated every 5 years (LfULG, 2018d).					
Currentness	In comparison to other states the published plot factsheets have a high currency (Barth and Forberg, 2015).					
Access	Data of the long-term soil monitoring are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the LfULG under consideration of farmers' privacy. The LfULG presents on its website parameter maps for the topsoil and the subsoil with results of the soil monitoring published 2014 (polychlorinated biphenyl, hexachlorbenzene, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, naphthalin). The spatial information is available in form of a WMS-layer at the Geoportal Sachsenatlas. The ArcGIS-layer is freely available online via the ArcGIS-Services of the LfULG Saxonia. The attributes of the layer can be requested but not processed, the content is provided by the server http://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services .					

1.2.28	Long-term soil monitoring Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAU	2017	-	-
Description	The long-term soil monitoring is realized by the State Office for Environmental Protection (LAU) since 1990 every 4-6 years, the latest in 2015 on 30 arable plots, 15 forest plots, 8 grassland plots and 3 fallow plots.					
Interoperability	Detailed measurement results are available, but not in a machine-readable format.					
Access	The LAU provides comprehensive description in PDF-format about each plot (LfU-ST, 2017) including spatial information (UTM32, three-digit/four-digit) and analysis results (2002) about earthworm stock, microbial biomass, soil respiration, organic pollutants (PCDD/F, PAK, HCB, beta-HCH, PCB6), heavy metal immission, anion/cation.					

1.2.29	Long-term soil monitoring Schleswig-Holstein	DE-SH	LLUR	2014	-	-
Description	In Schleswig-Holstein the long-term soil monitoring was installed in 1989 and 1996 by the LLUR. Since then, the State Office observes 37 basic plots (15 arable sites, 12 grassland, 5 forest, 5 special use) including 5 intensives since 2003 (39 basic plots until 2012). The analysis results are stored in a specific information system for soil.					
Supplement	The monitoring is supplemented by soil biological measurements (LLUR, 2014). The BDF-methodology and concept were evaluated in a scientific project in 2007-2010 and published with detailed information in a final report (Nerger, 2014).					
Access	The location of the long-term soil monitoring sites is displayed in the web map application "Landwirtschafts- und Umweltatlas". The results of the soil monitoring are published by the LLUR in detailed reports. Data of the long-term soil monitoring are available on request and as a subject to agreement with the LLUR under consideration of farmers' privacy.					

1.2.30	Long-term soil monitoring in Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	2006	-	-
Description	The long-term soil monitoring was installed in 1992 in cooperation of the TLUG, the State Institutes for Agriculture (TLL) and for Forest, Hunting and Fishery (TLWJF). The starting years of the individual plots varies between 1992 and 2004, while the most plots are implemented in the 1990s. In 2017 32 plots (14 arable sites, 9 grassland, 9 forest) including 4 intensive plots were observed. The concept for the plot selection is determined by representativeness concerning land use, soil landscape and threatening.					
Access	The website of the TLUG presents reports with detailed information about each plot and about analysis results (TLUG, 2006a,). The monitoring results were published by the State Office in 1998 as intern report for a measurement period up to 5 years and in 2006 as official report (so far, the most current report) for a measurement period up to 12 years (TLUG, 2006b).					

2. Soil map products

2.1 Basic soil properties

A reliable map product for the global scale is the state-of-the-art database Harmonized World Soil Database v1.2 presented by the [FAO Soils Portal](#), which is an improved digitized map product based on the previous map FAO/UNESCO Digital Soil Map of the World at the scale of 1:5,000,000 (FAO/UNESCO, 1971-1981). The most recent project by ISRIC-World Soil Information is a global compilation of soil profiles in a Global Soil Information System called “SoilGrids”, which was initially published in a predicted 1 km-raster, then in a 250 m-raster and will be continued by a raster of about 30 m in the future.

The European Soil Database is the central part of the European Soil Information System (EUSIS) and is managed by the [European Soil Data Centre \(ESDAC\)](#). It includes four sub-databases: The Soil Geographical Database of Eurasia (SGDBE), the PedoTransfer Rules Database (PTRDB), the Soil Profile Analytical Database of Europe (SPADBE) and the Database of Hydraulic Properties of European Soils (HYPRES). The data of the latter are not released by the contributing institutions. The [European Soil Data Centre \(ESDAC\)](#) provides further several derived maps illustrating soil properties, threats and functions and results of European research projects.

<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/topsoil-physical-properties-europe-based-lucas-topsoil-data>

For purposes at the level of Germany the soil map at the scale of 1:200,000 which is provided by the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR) is the highest resolved homogeneous map series that has been completed recently. Most of the federal states of Germany published soil maps at the scale of 1:50,000 or 1:25,000, respectively, but these are based on different methodology and concepts, and the usability for nation-wide analysis is limited. Maps for single federal states of a smaller scale than 1:200,000 were not considered in this report, even if they may provide another generalization approach than the Soil Map BÜK200. The federal states operate own spatial data infrastructures to manage and present the data and their metadata produced by the states’ agencies. All metadata of the digital data and services stored in these infrastructures are automatically integrated in a central metadata information system called Geodatenkatalog.de and accessible via the web interface of [Geoportal.de](#). It is part of the German Geodata Infrastructure (GDI-DE) which is connected to the European catalogue and portal for spatial data INSPIRE. The metadata schema (INSPIRE schema) of the data sets is equal but they differ in their content’s quality and completeness.

2.1.1	Harmonized World Soil Database v1.2	Global	FAO	2012	Raster database	30"
Description	<p>The map is an updated version of the FAO-UNESCO Soil Map of the World (FAO/UNESCO, 1971-1981) 1:5,000,000 with the goal to harmonize and combine existing regional and national soil information. Further included information are: various regional SOTER databases, Soil parameter estimates based on the World Inventory of Soil Emission Potential (WISE) database, the European Soil Database and the Soil Map of China 1:1 Million. ISRIC-World Soil Information, the European Soil Bureau Network (ESBN) and the Chinese Academy of Science – Institute of Soil Science were assigned for implementation. The data entry in a GIS was made by the International Institute of Applied System Analysis (IIASA). Detailed information is documented in the report ‘Harmonized World Soil Database v1.2’ (FAO et al., 2012).</p>					
Resolution	<p>Differences in detail and quality of primary soil information resulted in a variable resolution of the product presented in the database.</p>					
Completeness	<p>The very few missing data values in the source databases were replaced with data extracted from the most appropriate neighboring units having the same soil type.</p>					
Access	<p>The dataset is available via the FAO Soils Portal: http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/soil-survey/soil-maps-and-databases/harmonized-world-soil-database-v12/en/</p> <p>The data viewer program has to be installed to visualize the data. The datasets for slope, land use and soil quality in 5' resolution can be downloaded directly from the website in RAR-file format and ASCII-format.</p> <p>A regridded version was published in 2014 including additional calculated parameters (e.g. area weighted soil organic carbon (kg C per m²), in the resolution 0.05-degree as NetCDF files (Wieder et al., 2014).</p>					

2.1.2	SoilGrids	Global	ISRIC	2014	Raster	1 km; 250 m
Description	<p>SoilGrids is an updatable collection of soil property and class maps of the world which are a product of automatically processed soil profile data by machine-learning techniques (Hengl et al., 2017). SoilGrids is based on the initiative <i>GlobalSoilMap</i> as a contribution to the Global Soil Partnership initiative and for developing a globally distributed soil profile database (with data being managed by the data owners) and strengthen the effort for rescuing legacy soil profile data and compile their information under a common standard. The <i>GlobalSoilMap</i> group has the goal to merge these soil profile data to a global geographically continuous and updateable soil property map in gridded format without access to the original data. The <i>GlobalSoilMap</i> group was formed as an outgrowth of the International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS) Working Group for Digital Soil Mapping, initiated in 2006 and resulting in a <i>GlobalSoilMap</i> consortium agreement (Arrouays et al., 2017). The first global soil property map was released at limited resolution of about 1 km in 2014 and was generated using Generalized Linear Models. This was followed by an update at resolution of 250 m in 2017 fully based on Machine Learning. By the end of 2020 a worldwide product at 3" (arcsec) resolution will be published (about 90 m). This approach to global soil mapping is also referred to as "top-down" mapping (in contrast to "bottom-up" mapping where series of independent predictions are generated and then merged to create a global map) (Hengl et al., 2014; Hengl et al., 2017).</p>					

- Completeness** ThSoilGrids layers are of limited thematic (wide confidence limits) and spatial accuracy and contain artefacts and missing pixels (Hengl et al., 2017). This limits reusability. The authors invite all scientists to improve these maps by submitting a validation report or by contributing georeferenced soil profiles (points) and covariate data (raster with global coverage at resolutions of 250 m or better).
- Currentness** As soon as they receive a sufficient number of validation reports and/or new ground observations, they will re-run the predictions to produce an updated version of SoilGrids. Each GeoTiff available from the SoilGrids.org website carries the production date in the metadata, enabling different versions of the maps to be traced and compared.
- Access** SoilGrids data (GeoTiffs) can be obtained either via the web-mapping interface at www.soilgrids.org, via FTP, via the REST service and/or via a smartphone App. To download the complete global maps, use the FTP service ([ftp.soilgrids.org](ftp://ftp.soilgrids.org)).

2.1.3	European Soil Database v2.0 – Soil Geographical Database	Europe, Eurasia	JRC	2004 (raster 2006)	Polygon/ Raster	1:1,000,000/ 1 km
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- Description** The Soil Geographical Database of Eurasia at scale 1:1,000,000 (SGDBE) is part of the European Soil Database within the European Soil Information System (EUSIS) and a simplified representation of the European soil coverage. The spatial soil data are provided in vector format with attributes and in 1 km x 1 km and 10 km x 10 km raster format. The SGDBE consists of both a geometrical dataset and a semantic dataset (set of attribute files). The soils are defined by the soil codes of the Soil Typological Units (STU) from the 1974 (modified CEC 1985) FAO-UNESCO Soil Legend (FAO/UNESCO, 1971-1981) and the 1990 FAO-UNESCO Soil Legend. The STUs are described by variables (attributes) including the FAO soil name, the topsoil texture class, slope, parent material, phase, land use, elevation and the accumulated mean annual temperature class. For the geographical representation at a scale corresponding to the 1:1,000,000 the STUs are grouped into Soil Mapping Units (SMU). For detailed information about the metadata, attributes and use of the database see the ESDB v2.0 CD-ROM (JRC, 2012). The PedoTransfer Rules Database (PTRDB) presents methods and processes for the environmental interpretation and to facilitate the use of the Soil Database and to derive soil parameters like organic carbon content, cation exchange capacity, base saturation and other chemical and mechanical attributes based on the input attributes of the SGDBE (Daroussin and King, 1996). The ESDAC published in 2013 additional layers (polygon unit = STU) with derived data from the European Soil Database in combination with the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) and the Soil and Terrain Database (SOTER) for: depth available to roots, clay content, sand content silt content, organic carbon content, bulk density coarse fragments, total available water content from PTR and PTF (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-derived-data>).
- Resolution** In Germany the STU outlines match the units of the dominant soil types (*Leitbodenart*) of the German soil map BÜK1000 to a great extent, while the latter is more detailed.
- Validity** The data were extracted from national archives and in most countries the soil units and classifications systems differ significantly from the FAO system which was used for this dataset. So, the national data were re-interpreted to ‘fit’ the European system (last revision 1990-1997). The polygons are only representations of the

soils (but the best that currently exists for whole Europe at this scale) but no systematic checks on the content and integrity of the polygons (e.g. border harmonization) have been made so far (JRC, 2003).

Access is provided free of charge via [ESDAC](https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v20-vector-and-attribute-data) but must be requested with an online request form. The vector data are provided in SHAPE-format and DBF-format: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v20-vector-and-attribute-data> and the raster data are ESRI GRIDs: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v2-raster-library-1kxm1km>
The SHAPE files are also accessible via the URL https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ESDB_Archive/ESDB_Data_Distribution/ESDB_Data_full_distribution/ESDB_data_vx.cfm

2.1.4	Land use-stratified soil map of Germany 1:1,000,000 (BÜK1000N)	Germany	BGR	2005	Polygon	1:1,000,000
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Description The BÜK1000N shows the distribution of the dominant and attributed soils (*Leit- und Begleitböden*) distinguished according to the generalized land use classed arable area, grassland and forest (CORINE Land Cover 1990). In a first step, the land use information was intersected with the soil map units of the BÜK1000. In another working step, the descriptions of the soil legend units were adopted and representative soil profiles under forest, cropland and grassland were derived (Richter, 2013). Data from the BGR soil profile data base and from the medium-scale soil data of the German federal states as well as soil profiles from the National Forest Soil Survey (*BZE Wald*) were included. The results are stored in a relational database which is part of the BGR soil information system *FISBo BGR* (Richter, 2013). There are separate datasets for the arable areas, the grassland sites and the forest sites available.

Validity The map is a product of intensive cooperation by the BGR, the University of Applied Science in Eberswalde, the Federal Agency for Forestry and Wood Industry, the AG Boden and the federal forest research institutes. This process improves the interpretation and content access (Richter et al., 2007).

Currentness The map was revised 2013-02-22 to enhance the spatial precision (Richter, 2013). It's currently the most resolved and homogeneous map product for Germany combining land use and soil information available.

Supplement Access A booklet with explanations for BÜK1000N was published by Richter et al. (2007). The map is provided without registration and free of charge in ESRI-SHAPE format and as ESRI-GDB via the [Produktcenter](#) of the BGR. The profile data are stored in a soil profile data base (MS Access-DB) including 76 forest reference profiles, each with 3 parameters related to soil forms and 23 parameters related to horizons, 78 field reference profiles and 56 grassland reference profiles, each with 3 parameters related to soil forms and 16 to horizons.

SHAPE-
URL: https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/BUK1000N/Acker/pdf/buek1000n_Acker_v231.zip
MDB-URL (Profile-DB): https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/BUK1000N/Acker/mdb/buek1000n_Acker_v231.zip

2.1.5	Soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200)	Germany	BGR/ SGD	1998 - 2018	Polygon	1:200,000
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Description	Soil map 1: 200.000 represents the distribution and association of the soils as well as their characteristics in a homogeneous map for Germany. The BGR developed the BÜK200 since 1995 in co-operation with the Federal Geological Surveys of the states (SGD). The map is published in accordance with the Topographic Survey Map 1: 200,000 (TÜK200) in 55 individual map sheets (BGR, 2018).
Currentness	The BÜK200 currently offers the highest possible level of detail for nationwide issues without sheet lines.
Access	The maps are provided without registration and free of charge at the Produktcenter of the BGR in the formats SHAPE, TIFF, PNG, and PDF. WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/buek200/

2.1.6	General geological map of the Federal Republic of Germany (GÜK200)	Germany	BGR/ SGD	2007	Polygon	1:200,000
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Description	The map series GÜK200 is the result of cooperation between the BGR, the SGDs and the Geological Surveys of neighboring countries. The geological units are saved as discrete layers and contain information on stratigraphy, genesis and petrography of the rocks.
Currentness	At the moment, the GÜK200 data are being converted to the scale of 1: 250,000.
Supplement	The BGR published an overview to facilitate the use of the large number – 3,800 – of legend units (BGR and SGD, 2015).
Access	The 55 map sheets are provided without registration and free of charge at the Produktcenter of the BGR in the formats SHAPE, TIFF, PNG and PDF. WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/geologie/guek200/

2.1.7	Medium-scale Agricultural Site Mapping (MMK)	Eastern Germany	FZB	1981	Polygon	1:100,000
Description	The MMK is a map with pedological information for agricultural sites. It was developed in the years 1974 to 1981 under the direction of the department of Soil Science Eberswalde of the Research Center for Soil Fertility (FZB). Today's value of this map is on the one hand the informative value for certain scales and on the other hand the fact that a map work developed according to recent nomenclatures on a comparable or larger scale for the agricultural area is still missing or in progress in the eastern German states (LGB-BB, 2018).					
Validity	The MMK's target scale was 1: 100,000. The survey units and their boundaries were digitized in accordance with the working maps (topographical maps 1: 25,000, issue before 1945, with the borderlines of the breeding units). These formed the basis for the printed maps at a scale of 1: 100,000 whose topography was biased for reasons of secrecy. After 1990, these data were transferred in GIS by the BGR by smoothing the contouring of individual areas in case of overlapping, gussets or mirrored areas (due to the technical survey method) (LGB-BB, 2018).					
Supplement	In the form of the documentation sheet A, extensive area descriptions are available digitally, which enable thematic edits.					
Access	In Brandenburg the map is freely available in WMS and WFS format. In all other Eastern German States, the map is provided after request. WMS-URL for Brandenburg: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bokarten_wfs?					

2.1.8	Soil map BK50 (GeoLa) for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2012	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	Since 2003, the LGRB has been carrying out the pedological survey on a scale of 1: 50,000 (BK50). Together with the data of the Geological Map 1: 50,000 (GK50) they form the basis of the program <i>Integrierte Geowissenschaftliche Landesaufnahme</i> (GeoLa). The product provides information on soil genesis, soil type, source rock, relief and dominant soil profiles as well as physico-chemical soil characteristics and the assessment of soil functions (see record 6.9 for details) (LUBW, 2010).					
Currentness	The GeoLa-program for the topics soil science and geology was finished at the end of 2014. The GeoLa dataset is continuously updated.					
Validity	GeoLa uses a wide variety of information sources. In addition to analogue and digital archive and map documents of various scales, site surveys were also carried out (LGRB, 2018).					
Access	The data are a subject to charges but can be used for scientific purpose with an individual user agreement. They are listed online under http://lgrb-bw.de/aufgaben_lgrb/geola/produkte_geola WMS-URL: http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE=WMS&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_geola_bod					

2.1.9	General soil map 1:25 000 (ÜBK25) for Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2013	Polygon	1:25 000
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Description	The General soil map 1: 25.000 (<i>Übersichtsbodenkarte</i> ÜBK25) is derived from existing documents and was reviewed and supplemented by survey inspections in the field. The ÜBK25 is without sheet lines, is available for the whole state area of Bavaria and has a consistent legend about all map sheets. For an enhanced processability, the dataset is divided according to the TK25 map sheets.
Currentness	The map is updated as necessary, not with a fixed return routine. The most current version was published in February 2017.
Validity	The delineation and description of the ground units is verified and supported by 300 to 800 soil profile descriptions (LfU Bayern, 2017).
Access	All 613 map sheets are displayed in <i>UmweltAtlas Bayern</i> and are available in separate files for download as vector data in SHAPE format free of charge at the GeoPortal Bayern. In addition, the map is also available as WMS-layer. License: CC BY 3.0. WMS-URL: http://www.lfu.bayern.de/gdi/wms/boden/uebk25? Shape files: http://www.lfu.bayern.de/gdi/dls/daten/uebk25/uebk25_7546_epsg4258.zip http://www.lfu.bayern.de/gdi/dls/daten/uebk25/uebk25_7530_epsg31468.zip

2.1.10	Soil-geological map (BK50) for Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	in progress	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The Soil Geological Map is still in progress. Already published: Sheet L3744 (Potsdam). In progress are the map sheets L3746, L3140 and L3350.
Currentness	This is currently the highest resolved pedo-geological map work which was developed by the LBGR.
Access	WMS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bokarten_wms?language=ger&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS Please note: The BK 50 is currently not available in this service and will be added later. WFS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bokarten_wfs?

2.1.11	Areal soil data ('Bodenflächendaten' BFD50) for Hesse	DE-HE	HLNUG	2002	Vector	1:50,000
Description	The BDF50 is based on surveys in the years 1987-1995 and on field data of the 1960s and 1980s. In 2017 three WMS layers were derived from the soil data of the BFD50 map: the nitrate retention capacity of the soil (coloured classes from green – very low to red – very high), the yield potential and the site classification for biotope development. The dataset is INSPIRE-identified.					
Supplement	On its website the HLNUG provides comprehensive meta-information about the lineage of the data, e.g. the names of the mapping persons and the regional scale of the base-maps.					
Access	The map is available without registration at the INSPIRE geoportal, the Geoportal Hesse and Geoportal.de . Free use of the service for private purposes is allowed. The commercial use of the data is prohibited. Yield potential: http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wms.php?inspire=1&layer_id=43580&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS&INSPIRE=1 Nitrate retention capacity: http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wms.php?inspire=1&layer_id=43579&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS&INSPIRE=1 Main soil texture groups (<i>Bodenhauptgruppen</i>): http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wms.php?inspire=1&layer_id=43581&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS&INSPIRE=1 BFD50: http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wms.php?inspire=1&layer_id=43582&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS&INSPIRE=1					

2.1.12	Soil map 1:50,000 (BK50) for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2017	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	The map project (2003-2017) is the most recent soil map for Lower Saxony and replaced the BÜK50. In a standardized process a number of data were integrated (GK50, pedo-regional zonation, German soil taxation , forest site survey, DEM25, groundwater surface distance, profile data, ATKIS, etc.).					
Completeness	The BK50 has 13,000 legend units and 196,000 areas and shows a high grade of spatial and information detail (concerning areas, horizons and land use).					
Validity	The BK50 is closely coordinated in terms of location and content with other nationwide maps or databases. A uniform set of rules guarantees a comparable quality statewide.					
Access	The map layer is available as WMS at the <i>NIBIS-Kartenserver</i> of the LBEG. The attributed note box provides a WMS-URL: http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=989&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&					

2.1.13	'Konzeptbodenkarte' (KBK25) for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	1996/ 2017	Polygon	1:25,000
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Description	The KBK25 is a basic working map derived from data of state-wide soil survey programs (Bodenschätzung , Forstliche Standortskartierung , Bodenkundliche Landesaufnahme). In combination with the GK50 and other sources, it is also the main information base for the development of a soil map at the scale 1:50,000.
Currentness	With the creation of the soil map 1: 50 000 (BK50) the KBK25 is also being updated.
Validity	At the map sheet boundaries to unprocessed map sheets, distortions of the polygon contours and differences in content may occur (LUNG, 2016a).
Access	The KBK25 is not freely accessible and its usage is a subject to individual agreements with the LUNG.

2.1.14	Soil map 1:50,000 (IS BK 50) for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The dataset includes the soil map with the soil units, generalized soil type and soil texture groups of the topsoil (GD-NW, 2016). Further, a number of derived maps are included (see records 2.13, 3.13, 5.9 and 6.14 in this report).
Completeness	The map is complete except small residual areas in the border area to the neighboring state Lower Saxony.
Currentness	On 2018-03-15 the service was extensively updated.
Access	The dataset is INSPIRE-identified and available as WMS and AtomFeed/ SHAPE via the Geoportal.NRW and the Geological Survey GD-NW (Download service: www.tim-online.nrw.de). License: dl-de/by-2-0. WMS-URL: https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk050? AtomFeed: https://www.gis-rest.nrw.de/atomFeed/rest/atom/5c120c49-1486-4fc0-827c-da14624af4a4 SHAPE- URL: https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK50/ISBK50_EPSG25832_Shape.zip

2.1.15	Soil map 1:5,000 (IS BK 5) for agricultural areas in North Rhine-Westphalia	1/2 of DE-NW	GD-NW	2001-2018	Polygon	1:5,000
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Description	The map is based on results of the agricultural and forest site survey of the Geological Survey GD-NW with a dense soil profile network (100 m distances). The processing of the soil maps for site exploration is not in accordance with the map sheets of the <i>Deutsche Grundkarte</i> 1:5,000, but with boundaries of spatial units of specific interest (e.g. boundaries of municipalities, districts, water protection or nature reserves). For the mapping of the agricultural site exploration, all areas with agriculture use or potential agricultural use are processed.
Completeness	The data are supplied without topography. The map is available only for 70% of the states' agricultural area.
Access	The Geoportal.NRW and Geoportal.de provide a WMS and dataset via ATOM-Feed which visualizes the availability and the year of map creation of the digital and analogue maps for agricultural and forestry sites (https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk05_uebersichtskarte? ; https://www.opengeodat.a.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK5UEB/ISBK5UEB_EPSG25832_Geodata_base.zip). For ordering the dataset, a user agreement is obligatory. It is recommended to order the topographic grid data of the <i>Bezirksregierung Köln/Abt. 7 Geobasis</i> (www.lverma.nrw.de) directly at the Geological Survey GD-NW. A complete dataset as an excerpt from the information system usually includes the following contents and data formats: - digital soil map (soil type, soil structure in the single horizons, water conditions) as a PDF file - soil and evaluation maps in ALK-GIAP or ArcGIS (SHAPE) format (others on request) - explanations with textual evaluation of soil conditions (e.g. soil profile descriptions) as print or PDF file - General information on the basics of large-scale soil mapping as PDF file and interactive MS PowerPoint presentation - Soil and evaluation maps as color plot (on request). The website of the GD-NW provides test-dataset with this material (for agricultural sites: https://www.gd.nrw.de/zip/Demo-BK5_W0106.zip).

For Rhineland-Palatinate there are no medium-scale soil maps with basic soil properties available (>1:200,000). The LGB provides derived soil maps at the scale 1:50,000 (BFD50/200, see record 2.14, 5.10 and 6.15) and at the scale 1:5,000 for agricultural areas (BFD5L, see record 6.11).

2.1.16	Soil map 1:100,000 (BÜK100), Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2001	Polygon	1:100,000
Description	The soil map at a scale of 1:100,000 shows the distribution of the soils and soil communities in the Saarland. It contains 41 soil units, settlement areas and anthropogenic severe transformed areas are shown in their own symbology. The map is supplemented by a supplementary volume with a detailed description of the soil units (LUA, 2001).					
Validity	The BÜK100 is a product of the generalization of the preceding map project BÜK25.					
Access	The map layer are accessible by WMS and WFS via INSPIRE and Geoportal.saarland. WMC-URL: http://geoportal.saarland.de/mapbender/geoportal/mod_index.php?mb_user_myGui=Geoportal-SL&WMC=3023 WFS-URL: http://geoportal.saarland.de/arcgis/services/Internet/Boden_WFS/MapServer/WFSServer?request=DescribeFeatureType%26version=1.1.0%26typename=Bodenubersichtskarte					

2.1.17	Digital soil map 1:50,000 (BK50/ digBK50) for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2012	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	The BK50 is a soil scientific map for the Free State of Saxony. The legend units are represented by dominant and attributed soils (soil type and substrate type), supplemented by profile information and characteristics of the soil unit. This map is based on the 54 individual sheets of the states' area, produced during the last 20 years (Strohbach, F., 2018).					
Currentness	Currently, all dominant soil type profiles are analyzed by laboratory analysis and the latest knowledge is incorporated in the dataset (Strohbach, F., 2018).					
Resolution	The map shows different grades of detail depending on the source map sheet, e.g. the map sheet of Dresden shows a much finer differentiation of the dominant soil types.					
Access	The dataset is provided free of charge in SHAPE-format after request via the download service (https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/boden/27787.htm). The WMS and WFS are accessible via the Geoportal Sachsenatlas. WMS-URL: https://geoportal.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services/boden/bk50/MapServer/WmsServer? WFS-URL: https://geoportal.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services/boden/bk50/MapServer/WFSServer?					

2.1.18	Provisional soil map 1:50,000 (VBK50) for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2012	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	The digital areal soil information map 1:50,000 is based on digitized documents at the scales of 1:10,000/ 1:25,000, e.g. the working maps of Medium-scale Agricultural site Mapping 1:25,000 (MMK), the forest site mapping (Forstliche Standortskartierung) and large scale project-related survey programs. The input information was edited according to the areal requirements of the scale of 1:50,000. The polygons were associated with the dominant soil form. Areal records as standard profiles are hosted for further content-related characterization of legend units and for further analysis (LAGB, 2018). The WMS/WFS includes layer for the substrate types (<i>Substrattypen</i>), soil type communities (<i>Bodentypengesellschaften</i>), soil types (<i>Bodentypen</i>), soil classes (<i>Bodenklassen</i>) and basic soil data (<i>Bodenbasisdaten</i>) (LAGB, 2006; LAGB, 2014).					
Completeness	Two map sheets are not included in the VBK50 (Blankenburg, Nordhausen) (LAGB, 2017). The representation of the soil communities usual at this scale has been omitted due to the heterogeneous input documents (LAGB, 2018). The substrate type represents a strongly generalized form of the dominant substrate conditions. The legend definition of the WMS layer and the codes included in the layer <i>Bodenbasisdaten</i> is not included in the WMS (see WFS for values).					
Currentness	The codes for the layer <i>Bodenbasisdaten</i> are based on the four-digit KA4-Coding (AG Boden, 1994). For transformation into KA5 (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) see transformation tool published by the BGR (BGR, 2013).					
Access	The soil map is INSPIRE-identified and freely available via the Geoportal.de as WMS: https://www.geodatenportal.sachsen-anhalt.de/gfds/ws/wms/16254a31-2174-88e1/GDI-LSA_LAGB_BASIS_BK50/ows.wms? and WFS: https://www.geodatenportal.sachsen-anhalt.de/gfds/ws/wfs/7217a44b-3bb8-21f7/GDI-LSA_LAGB_BASISDATEN/ows.wfs? .					

2.1.19	Soil-geological survey map (BGKK100) for Thuringia	DE-TH	TLUG	2000	Polygon	1: 100,000
Description	The Soil-geological Survey Map 1: 100,000 was developed on the basis of existing documents and maps. These are: Geological maps 1: 25,000, the German soil taxation supplemented by the soil profile descriptions of the appraisal books and selective land surveys (obtained by expert opinions, scientific papers and field trips). Forest site maps (1: 10,000) were used for larger forest areas. The mapping units are designed as soil associations. The structure scheme refers essentially to the substrate properties of the parent rocks, in floodplains and lowlands to the groundwater influence.					
Currentness	An approximation of the dominant soil types to the nomenclature of KA4 (AG Boden, 1994) was added to the legend later.					
Access	The map is meant to be directly exported without registration and free of charge in SHAPE-format at the web map application of the TLUG (http://www.tlug-jena.de/kartendienste/) but the folder is empty.					

2.2 Soil Biology

The influence and value of soil fauna and soil microbiomes for a sustainable soil management is enormous. In contrast to that fact, the availability of data is inadequate. For Germany there two important data repositories established: *Edaphobase*, which collects and publishes data about soil invertebrates (see record [1.1.7](#)), and the *Exploratories for Biodiversity*, collecting sample data about fungi and microalgae and microarthropodae (see record [1.1.8](#)). Beyond that, several data infrastructures exist or are in preparation but have limited accessibility, findability and interoperability. The Soil Biodiversity map of the Global Soil Biodiversity Atlas Maps visualizes the soil microbial diversity based on the distribution of microbial soil carbon (Orgiazzi et al., 2016a). This approach was developed by Serna-Chavez and colleagues (Serna-Chavez et al., 2013). At the European level, the ESADC presents a map of potential threats to soil biodiversity (Orgiazzi et al., 2016b), which is also included in the publication of the European Atlas of Soil Biodiversity (Jeffery et al., 2010). The latter shows distribution maps for Europe at the national scale. An equivalent at the global scale is the Global Soil Biodiversity Atlas (Orgiazzi et al., 2016a). But all these mapping approaches declare a lack of indicator definitions for assessing soil biodiversity. The main source for research data in the field of soil-zoology in Germany is the data warehouse Edaphobase. For soil biological data provided by German state institutions, the long-term soil monitoring is the only program where the systematically observation of soil biological parameters is intended.

2.3 Soil Hydrology

The availability of derived soil hydrological data in Germany is equivalent to the basic soil property data availability and often both were provided all in one data set. Derived soil hydrological maps at a larger scale than 1:1,000,000 are in preparation by the German State Agency BGR, based on the current soil map at the scale 1:200,000 (BÜK200). Most of the federal states provide derived hydrological soil properties at the scale 1:200,000 and larger. Even if the methodology which was processed in the federal states is comparable, the basic soil units are products of diverging concepts.

2.3.1	A global dataset of soil hydraulic properties and sub-grid variability of soil water retention and hydraulic conductivity curves	Global	Montzka, C. et al.	2017	Raster	0.25°
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Description The global dataset is based on the ROSETTA pedotransfer function of Schaap et al. (2001) applied to the SoilGrids1km dataset of Hengl et al. (2014) with the goal to scale van Genuchten hydraulic parameters (θ_s , θ_r , α , n , K_s) to individual model grids (Montzka et al., 2017)).

Validity The method used for the resampling of soil hydraulic properties to a model grid promises a higher precision compared to typically performed aggregation approaches such as spatial averaging and the use of dominant textural properties or soil classes.

Access The dataset is published in NetCDF-format via PANGAEA and available there (<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.870605>) under the CC BY 3.0 license.

2.3.2	ESA Climate Change Initiative - Soil Moisture (CCI SM v04.4)	Global	ESA	2018	Raster	0.25°
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Description The Soil Moisture CCI project was part of the ESA Programme on Global Monitoring of Essential Climate Variables (ECV), also known as the Climate Change Initiative (CCI), initiated in 2010 for a period of 6 years. The project focuses on C-band scatterometers (ERS-1/2 scatterometer, METOP Advanced Scatterometer) and multi-frequency radiometers (SMMR, SSM/I, TMI, AMSR-E, Windsat). The data set covers the (nearly) 40 year period from 1978 to 30.6.2018 and consists of three products: an active data set, a passive data set and a combined data set (ESA, 2012).

Resolution The temporal resolution is daily.

Access The most current data set version as well as previous product versions are available after user registration (verification of the user request is manually checked, so it takes some time) at the website of the ESA Climate Change Initiative:
<https://www.esa-soilmoisture-cci.org/node/145>

2.3.3	3D Soil Hydraulic Database of Europe	Europe	JRC	2017	Raster	1 km; 250 m
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Description The European Soil Hydraulic Database (EU-SoilHydroGrids ver1.0) was derived by using the functions of the European Pedotransfer Rules (Tóth et al., 2017). The data are based on physical, chemical and taxonomical data of the SoilGrids250m and 1 km: clay, silt and sand content (mass %), organic carbon content (g kg⁻¹); bulk density (kg m⁻³); pH in water and depth to bedrock (cm) at 0, 5, 15, 30, 60, 100, and 200 cm depth. For these seven standard depths 16 soil hydraulic properties were calculated at both 250 m and 1 km resolutions:

- water content at field capacity;
- saturated hydraulic conductivity;
- hydraulic conductivity curve;
- saturated water content;
- water content at wilting point;
- moisture retention curve

Validity In comparison with the soil hydraulic properties available from the European Soil Database (EU-HYDI, about 1500 samples) the predictions of the EU-SoilHydroGrids shows a better performance due to a wider and more detailed range of soil properties. Further advantages are the determined resolution (instead of polygons of soil types) and that the properties are provided at seven soil depths (Tóth et al., 2017).

Access The data are provided after request at the [ESDAC](https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/3d-soil-hydraulic-database-europe-1-km-and-250-m-resolution) in GeoTIFF format.
<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/3d-soil-hydraulic-database-europe-1-km-and-250-m-resolution>

2.3.4	Mean Annual Infiltration Rate of the Soil (HAD) in Germany	Germany	BfG	2013	Raster	1:25,000
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Description The map is part of the map compendium *Hydrologischer Atlas von Deutschland* (HAD). It includes layer for the mean annual infiltration rate, the surface runoff on arable soils, lakes and the position of not-assessed areas in grid format.

Completeness The WMS layer is provided without legend and detailed descriptions of the value classes.

Access WMS-URL: http://geoportal.bafg.de/wmsproxy/HAD/HAD_45?
 Web map application: <http://geoportal.bafg.de/mapapps2/resources/apps/HAD/index.html?lang=de>

2.3.5	Soil water balance for Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m
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Description The dataset (“Wasserhaushalt der Böden in Deutschland“) includes the following layers:
 a) Available water capacity in the rooting zone [mm];
 b) Air capacity [Vol.-%];
 c) Mean annual rate of percolation water of the soil [mm/a]
 d) Mean annual rate of capillary rise [mm/a]
 e) Amount of direct runoff on agricultural soils [mm/a]
 f) Plant available water in the summer half-year [mm]
 g) Exchange frequency of water in agricultural soils [%/a]
 h) Effective root penetration depth [dm]
 i) Field capacity up to 1 m depth [m]
 j) Mean groundwater level under surface.
 The theme maps are based on BÜK1000N (BGR), the DEM50 (BKG), climatic information of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) for the period 1961-1990 as well as on land use data from the dataset CORINE Land Cover 2006 (UBA). The method for f) is part of the TUB-BGR approach (Krug et al., 2003).

Completeness The datasets coverage is limited to areas in Germany under agricultural land use in 2006.

Currentness The mean annual rate of percolation (c) was processed one time with no regular updating so far. The method is currently processed by the BGR for the BÜK200 (Wessolek et al., 2003).
 For d): In contrast to older map products, climatic factors are taken into account in this evaluation (Duijnsveld, 2015).

Resolution For e): The SCS-curve number model needs more specific agricultural land use information than the CLC can provide. So the picture of the direct runoff is very coarse.

Access All layers are provided without registration and free of charge at the [Produktcenter](#) of the BGR in one WMS:
<https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/bodenwasserhaushalt/>
 The layers a – g are also published separately in GeoTIFF format at the Produktcenter of the BGR:
 a) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/NFKWE1000/geotiff/NFKWe1000_250.zip
 b) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/LKWE1000/geotiff/LKWe1000_250.zip
 c) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/SWR1000/geotiff/swr1000_250.zip
 d) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/KA1000/geotiff/KA1000_250.zip
 e) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/OAAcker1000/geotiff/OAAcker1000_250.zip
 f) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/WVPFL1000/geotiff/WVPFL1000_250.zip
 g) https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/AHACGL1000/geotiff/AHACGL1000_250.zip

2.3.6	Calculated daily, monthly and average monthly values for different characteristic elements of soil and crops	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Point	-
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Description	For different locations in Germany, values for soil moisture, soil temperatures, frost depth, evapotranspiration and evaporation of crops and grass were calculated from 1991-01-01 on. Time series of daily, monthly and average monthly values per station were calculated with the agrometeorological models AMBAV and AMBATI. For each station and parameter a txt-file is available containing mean monthly values.
Completeness	The time series can include inhomogeneities (i.e., caused by change of station location or instrument). Data users are urged to study the accompanying station metadata and the dataset descriptions.
Validity	The data are regularly versioned and under permanent quality control ("recent" have not yet been completed by the full quality control, while "historical" already have). The accuracy of the values depends on the quality of the models as well as on the quality of the model input.
Access	The data are available free of charge with consideration of the rights of use via the FTP-Server of the DWD Climate Data Center (CDC) (ftp://ftp-cdc.dwd.de/pub/CDC/observations_germany/). Every gzip compressed ASCII file contains a time series for one location. The parameters are given in columns separated by the delimiter ';'. The first row is the header.

2.3.7	Daily grids of soil temperature at 5 cm depth, version 0.x	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Raster	1 km
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Description	The grid is interpolated from the soil temperature which was measured at a fixed selection of stations. Only locations with complete datasets from 1991-01-01 on have been used. The soil temperature is calculated by the model AMBETI, which was developed at the agrometeorological research centre in Braunschweig (Braden, 2012). The interpolation method is a regional multiple linear regression with geographical longitude, latitude and height of location as input variables and a subsequent triangulation, covering Germany with a resolution of 1x1 km.
Interoperability	The metadata are so far not machine-readable or available via API.
Access	The access is free of charges with consideration of the rights of use (GeoNutzV, 2013) via the FTP-server of the DWD Climate Data Center (CDC) (ftp://ftp-cdc.dwd.de/pub/CDC/grids_germany/daily/soil_temperature_5cm/). The ASCII-files are packed as tar archive (Tarball) and compressed as GNU zip-file.

2.3.8	Daily grids of soil moisture under grass and sandy loam, version 0.x	Germany	DWD	(daily)	Raster	1 km
Description	The grid is interpolated from the soil moisture in 60 cm depth under grass which was measured at a fixed selection of stations. The equal number of stations with complete datasets from 1991-01-01 on has been used. The soil moisture under grass is calculated by the model AMBAV, which was developed at the Agrometeorological Research Centre (ZAMF) in Braunschweig (Friesland and Löpmeier, 2007). The interpolation method is a regional multiple linear regression with geographical longitude, latitude and height of location as input variables and a subsequent triangulation, covering Germany with a resolution of 1x1 km. Values are in percent plant useable water (% NFK), where the used soil has a wilting point of 13 volume% and a field capacity of 37 volume%.					
Validity	The grid's uncertainties are a result of the parameter calculation and of the interpolation process. From nearly 280 locations 360000 grid points were interpolated. As the soil moisture depends strongly on precipitation which has large spatial variability, the interpolated grids cannot be expected to be exact.					
Access	The access to the ASCII-files is free of charges with consideration of the rights of use via the FTP-server of the DWD Climate Data Center (CDC) (ftp://ftp-cdc.dwd.de/pub/CDC/grids_germany/daily/soil moist/)					

2.3.9	Derived soil property maps – Hydrology, Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m
Description	The maps are derived of the soil map 1:50,000 BK50 for Baden-Wuerttemberg within the program <i>Integrierte Geowissenschaftliche Landesaufnahme</i> (GeoLa). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity (FK) • Usable field capacity (nFK) • Air capacity (LK) • Saturated water conductivity (kf-value) • Potential cation exchange capacity (CEC/ KAKpot) These are processed by the use of survey data for soil texture, humus content and bulk density.					
Validity	Only dominant soils with a share of >25 % of the total area are considered in the process (LGRB, 2012).					
Access	The data are a subject to charges. They are listed online under http://lgrb-bw.de/aufgaben_lgrb/geola/produkte_geola WMS-URL: http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE=WMS&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_geola_bod					

2.3.10	Soil-hydrological map, Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2017	Raster	100 m
Description	The Soil-hydrological map outlines the dominant runoff processes (Horton runoff, saturated surface runoff, interflow and deep soak) using an expert-assisted method using soil, relief, and land use data.					
Validity	The soil hydrological units (BHE) are reproducible and may also be used outside of Baden-Württemberg.					
Supplement	The data bases used and the methodology are documented in detail in the LGRB-Fachbericht 2017/2 (LGRB, 2017a).					
Access	The map can be displayed in the LGRB-map viewer: http://maps.lgrb-bw.de/?view=lgrb_bhk or loaded as WMS. The data can be provided independently of the map sheet extent for any section or for specific administrative units.					

2.3.11	Pedological moisture level for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2017	Raster	50 m
Description	The map is derived on the basis of pedological, soil hydrological, geomorphological and climatic criteria. The derivation method does not consider indicator plants or plant communities and is thus also applicable to arable land or intensively used grassland (LGRB, 2017b).					
Access	The map can be displayed in the LGRB-map viewer (http://maps.lgrb-bw.de/?view=lgrb_bfs) or downloaded as WMS (http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_bfs).					

2.3.12	Infiltration water rate for Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2016	Polygon	1:25,000
Description	The mean infiltration water rate 1971-2000 is the result of site-differentiated soil water balance modeling with GWN-BW (Version 2 to Version 3.1). It corresponds to the water balance component of precipitation minus the sum of actual evaporation, runoff and refill of the ground reservoir. Surface drainage from unsealed surfaces was calculated using the CN method (USDA), and for sealed surfaces, depending on the degree of sealing. The infiltration rate used here does not consider capillary rise. The basis for the modeling are the following input data: Meteorology (station data of the DWD for temperature, humidity, sunshine duration and wind, regionalized grid data of the DWD for precipitation (REGNIE grid)); Digital terrain model DGM 25 (LfU); CORINE Land Cover 2000 (UBA); Digital Soil Map BÜK25 (LfU).					
Validity	In order to be able to fulfill the requirement to use state-wide uniform data, datasets from different scales were combined for modeling (e.g. DGM25, BK25, CLC 1:100,000). Furthermore, data with regional differences in quality (e.g. regionalized station data of the different climate parameters) were edited in preparation for the modelling.					
Access	The access is free for WMS-layer and for the dataset <i>Sickerwasserrate</i> (under CC BY 3.0) and provided via the 'UmweltAtlas Bayern': http://www.lfu.bayern.de/boden/index.htm .					

2.3.13	Derived hydrological parameter for agricultural areas (BFD5L), Hesse & Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-HE, DE-RP	HLNUG & LGB	2017	Polygon	1:5,000
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Description	<p>The BFD 5L was developed in the frame of the project ‘Bodenfunktionsbezogene Auswertung von Bodenschätzungsdaten’ in close cooperation of the HLNUG, the Regional Finance Office Koblenz, the LGB and the LVerGeo-RP and the <i>Ingenieurbüro Schnittstelle Boden</i>. As a basis, the data of the German soil taxation (Bodenschätzung) were used. The dataset beside other layers (see record 6.11):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity • Usable field capacity <p>For detailed methodological information see the report (HLNUG, 2012). The scale of the layers ranges from 1:2,000 to 1:50,000.</p>
Completeness	In the present first version (version 1.3.0, 2017) of the MapServer only evaluations based on the class sign of the soil estimate are used. Further theme maps, e.g. the potential erosion risk from water or the location typing for the biotope development, will follow and be integrated into the MapServer after completion of the work.
Validity	The database includes a software for plausibility check (syntax, semantics, conformity of the ‘Schätzungsbuch’ and the ‘Schätzungskarte’) (HLNUG and LGB, 2008).
Access	<p>The WMS is available without registration at the <i>Bodenviewer Hessen</i> and the LGB-map viewer. The datasets of the BFD5L are available for uncommercial use via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client as WFS.</p> <p>WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd5?</p> <p>WFS-URL: http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=2383&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS</p>

2.3.14	Groundwater depth isolines for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2016	Line	1:200,000
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Description	The map “Grundwasserhöhengleichen” shows the groundwater isolines of the top aquifer of the soil (LUNG, 2017a). The map was processed with ‘Detrended Kriging’ based on a geo-hydraulic model (for detailed information see LUNG, 2016b).
Access	<p>The dataset is available via the <i>Umweltkarten</i> geoportal for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania in WMS:</p> <p>https://www.umweltkarten.mv-regierung.de/script/mv_a7_hydrogeologie_wms.php?language=ger&</p> <p>WFS and SHAPE-file: https://www.umweltkarten.mv-regierung.de/files/dynamik.zip</p>

2.3.15	Soil-hydrological maps for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000
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Description	<p>The data background of the layers is the soil map 'Konzeptbodenkarte' 1:25,000 (KBK25) and the digital Basic-Landscape Model (LAIv). The dataset <i>Bodengeologie</i> includes a number of layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity (100 cm) • Usable field capacity (100 cm) • Air capacity
Access	<p>Available for visualization via the <i>Umweltkarten</i> geoportal for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and as WFS via the MetaVer-catalogue: https://www.umweltkarten.mv-regierung.de/script/mv_a7_bodengeologie_wfs.php?</p>

2.3.16	Derived maps based on the soil map BK50 for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2018	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	<p>Several maps were processed based on Lower Saxonian soil map 1:50,000 (BK50):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) <i>Pflanzenverfügbares Bodenwasser</i> - Availability of water to plants (WPFL): The map was derived by combining the usable field capacity in the effective root zone and the amount of capillary rise from the groundwater. Parameter: soil texture, bulk density, humus content, soil stratification, land use, groundwater level. The legend distinguishes 7 classes, starting with <50 mm-class up to >300 mm-class. b) <i>Grundwasserstufe</i> – Groundwater level: The groundwater level is derived by the parameters mean maximum and mean minimum groundwater level, expressed by a code in 7 classes (Mueller and Waldeck, 2011). c) <i>Nutzbare Feldkapazität im effektiven Wurzelraum</i> – usable field capacity in the effective root zone, in five classes. d) <i>Sickerwasserrate</i> – Infiltration rate (mm/a) was derived by the parameter plant-available soil water (soil map BK50), precipitation and potential evaporation (FAO) and land use information. For details see Mueller and Waldeck (2011). The values are grouped in 14 groups with class size of 50 mm/a, from 0 mm/a to >600 mm/a. e) <i>Austauschhäufigkeit des Bodenwassers</i> – Exchange frequency of soil water (per year), in five classes.
Validity	<p>The methodological description in publication by Mueller and Waldeck (2011) differs from the metadata description of the dataset.</p>
Access	<p>The map layer is available as WMS at the <i>NIBIS-Kartenserver</i> of the LBEG. The attributed note box provides an URL for the WMS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=998&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& b) https://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=1018&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& c) https://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=1019&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& d) http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=1022&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& e) http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=1023&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&

2.3.17	Derived soil hydrological maps based on the IS BK 50 for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The following maps were derived from the soil map 1:50,000 for North-Rhine Westfalia: Groundwater (bordering depth to groundwater; distance to the optimal depth to groundwater); water logging; capillary rise of groundwater; saturated water conductivity; cation exchange capacity; air capacity; field capacity; usable field capacity (GD-NW, 2016).
Completeness	The map is complete except small residual areas in the border area to the neighboring state Lower Saxony.
Currentness	On 2018-03-15 the service was extensively updated.
Access	The data are available in one layer set with the soil map as WMS and AtomFeed/SHAPE via the Geoportal.NRW and the Geological Survey GD-NW (Download service: www.tim-online.nrw.de). License: dl-de/by-2-0. WMS-URL: https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk050? AtomFeed: https://www.gis-rest.nrw.de/atomFeed/rest/atom/5c120c49-1486-4fc0-827c-da14624af4a4 SHAPE- URL: https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK50/ISBK50_EPSG25832_Shape.zip

2.3.18	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200) for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The dataset "Schutzwürdige und schutzbedürftige Böden" for the estimation of soil functions includes the following layers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soils influenced by groundwater and waterlogging („Grund-, stau- und hangnasse Böden“) • Potential percolation water amount (1961-90) ("Potentielle Sickerwasserspende")
Currentness	The methodology to assess the vulnerability of soils corresponds to the five classes which were applied for other federal states.
Supplement	Detailed information about the single soil functions, their parameter, processed data and methods are provided in a comprehensive report (MUF, 2005).
Access	The WMS and the WFS for each layer are accessible via Geoportal.rlp and via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client (CC BY-NC 3.0). WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd50_200? WFS-URL: http://www.geoportal.rlp.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=1741&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS

2.3.19	Derived hydrological maps (BÜK200) for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2002	Polygon	1:200,000
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Description	<p>The maps were derived based on the soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200) for Rhineland-Palatinate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity (100 cm) • Field capacity in the rooting layer • Usable field capacity (100 cm) • Usable field capacity in the rooting layer <p>Input data: risk for mineralization, potential for dry cracks development, field capacity, potential for back water influence (Friedrich and Vorderbrügge, 2002).</p>
Currentness	New derived maps of the soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200) for Germany published by the BGR will be available in the next future.
Access	The data are listed in the catalogue of the Geoportal.de and can be visualized via the WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd200?

2.3.20	Soil-hydrological maps (BÜK100), Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000
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Description	<p>The maps are based on the soil map of the Saarland BÜK100 and physical parameters of the states' profile database of the soil information system SAARBIS. Field capacity (up to 10 dm profile depth (FK10)) Air capacity (rated up to 10 dm profile depth (LK10)).</p>
Access	<p>A WMS including a set of layers is accessible via INSPIRE, via the Geoportal of the Saarland and the Geoportal.de. The reuse is free under consideration of LVGL-SL-User license. WMS-URL: http://geoportal.saarland.de/arcgis/services/Internet/Boden_Internet/MapServer/WmsServer?</p>

2.3.21	Soil-hydrological maps for Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2007	Polygon	1:200,000
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Description	<p>The database and map collection “Auswertekarten Bodenschutz” includes the following layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity (FK); • Usable field capacity (nFK); • Air capacity (LK); • Saturated water conductivity (kf-value); • Soil water balance (degree of watering, degree of saturation, infiltration); • Groundwater level <p>The derived data are processing results of the GÜK400, DEM20, long-term mean of the water balance (DWD), CORINE Land Cover 2000 and BÜK-SN200</p>
Validity	The maps are derived based on standardized methods (LfULG, 2007).
Reusability	The state office provides comprehensive metadata.
Access	<p>The data are provided on DVD in SHAPE-format and MS ACCESS-Database which can be obtained via the LfULG, Ref.42 (remainders). The geodata infrastructure GEOMIS-Sachsen provides additionally the</p> <p>WMS: https://geoportal.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services/boden/bbw50/MapServer/WMSServer?</p> <p>WFS-URL: http://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/infosysteme/wfs/services/boden/bbw50?</p>

2.3.22	Derived soil-hydrological maps based on the German soil taxation for Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2012	Polygon	1:10,000
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Description	<p>The database and map collection includes the following results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field capacity (FK); • Usable field capacity (nFK); • Air capacity (LK); • Saturated water conductivity (kf-value); • Potential cation exchange capacity (KAKpot) • Soil water balance (degree of watering, degree of saturation, infiltration); <p>The derived parameters are based on data of the German soil taxation (Bodenschätzung).</p>
Access	<p>The WFS is provided without restrictions via the <i>Geodatenportal Sachsen-Anhalt</i>: https://www.geodatenportal.sachsen-anhalt.de/gfds/ws/wfs/580c8e73-77e8-d023/GDI-LSA_LAGB_SCHAETZUNG_PARAMETER/ows.wfs?</p>

2.4 Soil Erosion

The following maps represent derived data and products of erosion models, illustrating the potential soil erosion risk by wind or water. Although, erosion is not included in the Bodium approach, the presented spatial datasets may refer to valuable soil-landscape developments and models.

2.4.1	Soil erosion risk assessment in Europe data (MESALES model) – Dataset	Europe	JRC	2002	Raster	1:1,000,000
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Description The Soil Erosion Risk Assessment data have been prepared by INRA (France) under contract to the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission using the MESALES model, as a pre-step of the PESERA project. The model concept is based on the land cover and land crust formation as key factors influencing runoff and erosion risk. The model uses empirical rules to combine data on land use (CORINE Land Cover database), soil crusting susceptibility, soil erodibility (determined by pedotransfer rules from the Soil Geographical Data Base of Europe at scale 1:1 Million), relief (USGS HYDRO1K digital elevation model), and meteorological data at a 1 x 1 km pixel size (Space Applications Institute, Ispra JRC). Spatial units for the presentation of results are defined using either administrative units or watershed catchment units (Le Bissonnais et al., 2002).

Currentness The data product has to be considered as an intermediate step towards an erosion model at the European scale, prior to the initiation of the PESERA project (Le Bissonnais, 2002). The Dataset was revised in 2017.

Access To get access to the data, the user has to compile the online request form at the [ESDAC](http://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu) portal. The data are offered in 5 grids (ESRI): annual, summer, winter, autumn and spring.

<http://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-erosion-risk-assessment-europe-data-mesales-model-dataset>

2.4.2	Soil erodibility (K- Factor) high resolution dataset	Europe	JRC	2014	Raster	500 m
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Description The dataset is a raster map of the soil erodibility in the European Union member states at 500 m resolution, created in 2014. It is derived on the basis of the LUCAS 2009 soil survey exercise and the European Soil Database.

Completeness The map incorporates certain improvements over the coarse-resolution map (10 km) version 2011 like the inclusion of soil structure and surface stone content for the K-factor estimation.

Validity The dataset is verified against local, regional and national data found in the literature (21 studies) (Panagos et al., 2014).

Access The public user can download 3 different datasets: a) Soil erodibility in Europe (K-factor), b) Soil Erodibility incorporating Stoniness (K-factor) and c) the Effect of Stoniness in K-factor (% reduction). To get access to the data, the user has to compile the online request form.

<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-erodibility-k-factor-high-resolution-dataset-europe>

2.4.3	Soil loss by water erosion (RUSLE2015)	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster	100 m
Description	The dataset (GIS map) is the result of applying a modified version of the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model, RUSLE 2015, applied for 2010. Input layers: LUCAS Topsoil, European Soil Database, Lucas Earth Observations, Rainfall Erosivity Database at European Scale (REDES), CORINE Land Cover 2006, COPERNICUS Remote Sensing, EUROSTAT (statistics on Crops, Tillage, Plant residues, cover crops), DEM25, Good Agricultural Environmental Condition (GAEC).					
Completeness	The modified version delivers improved estimates based on higher resolution (100 m compared to 1 km) and peer-reviewed inputs of rainfall, soil, topography, land use and management from the year 2010 (the latest year for which most of the input factors are estimated) (Panagos et al., 2015a).					
Resolution	This is the most detailed assessment yet of soil erosion by water for the EU28.					
Access	The map can be requested by an online request form free of charge at the ESDAC data portal: https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-erosion-water-rusle2015 ; https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/rusle2015					

2.4.4	Net erosion and sediment transport in Europe using WaTEM/SEDEM	EU28	JRC	2018	Raster	100 m
Description	The GIS-map visualizes the net soil erosion and deposition in European Union (EU28) for the year 2010 as a result of an application WaTEM/SEDEM model. The model includes RUSLE2015 soil erosion estimates and the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) at 25m (Borrelli et al., 2018).					
Supplement	The data are available also as 25 m raster for specific areas which must be requested from the authors.					
Access	To get access to the data, the user has to compile the online request form at the ESDAC portal . https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/estimate-net-erosion-and-sediment-transport-using-watemedem-european-union					

2.4.5	Cover management factor (C-factor) for the EU - LANDUM model	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster / Polygon	100 m
Description	The LANDUM model proposes a methodology for estimating the C-factor in the EU, based CORINE Land Cover data, biophysical attributes derived from remote sensing (MERIS Environmental Satellite sensor) and statistical data on agricultural crops and practices. In arable lands, the C-factor was estimated using crop statistics (% of land per crop) and data on management practices such as conservation tillage, plant residues and winter crop cover (Panagos, 2015b).					
Validity	Some of the input data have a much smaller resolution than the product, e.g. biophysical parameter layers (300 m), agricultural statistical data (NUTS2), which indicates a reduced precision at the local scale.					
Access	The product of the model is available in SHAPE- and raster format via the ESDAC portal after sending the request form: https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/cover-management-factor-c-factor-eu					

2.4.6	Soil risks (“Gefährdung der Böden in Deutschland”)	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m
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Description The following parameter are included as layers: Potential Arable Soil Erosion by water (t/ha*a); Erodibility of arable soils, K-Factor [(t/ha) / ((kJ/m²) * (mm/h))]; Rainfall Erosivity, R-Factor [(kJ/m²) * (mm/h)]; Slope factor, S-Factor; Potential risk for wind erosion on arable soils; Erodibility of soils by wind; Effective Bulk density in 35 cm depth [g/cm³]. The theme maps are based on BÜK1000N (BGR), the DEM50 (BKG), climatic information of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) for the period 1961-1990 as well as on land use data from the dataset CORINE Land Cover 2006 (UBA).

Completeness The datasets coverage is limited to areas in Germany under agricultural land use in 2006.

Access WMS-URL:
[https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/bodengefaehrdungen/?](https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/bodengefaehrdungen/)

2.4.7	Potential soil erosion risk on arable soils in Germany	Germany	BGR	2014	Raster	250 m
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Description The map “Potentielle Erosionsgefährdung der Ackerböden durch Wasser in Deutschland 1:1.000.000” shows the risk of soil loss due to surface runoff and splash erosion in Germany. It is based on pedological, relief and climatic factors (BÜK1000N, DEM50 (BKG), mean annual precipitation data 1961-1990 (DWD), CORINE Land Cover dataset 2006 (UBA/DRL)). The map was created by using the long-term model USLE (Universal Soil Loss Equation, DIN 19708:2005-02) which was adapted by the BGR for application with soil maps (Bug, 2014a).

Supplement The method is documented in the ‘MethodenWIKI Bodenkunde’ of the FISBo BGR <https://www.methodenwiki-bodenkunde.de>.

Access The map is provided without registration and free of charge at the [Produktcenter](#) of the BGR in the formats GeoTIFF, TIFF, PNG and PDF.
 GeoTIFF-
 URL: https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/PEGWASSER1000/pdf/pegwasser1000_250_v10.zip
 WMS-URL:
[https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/pegwasser1000/?](https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/pegwasser1000/)

2.4.8	Potential risk of wind erosion on arable soils in Germany	Germany	BGR	2014	Raster	250 m
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Description The map “Potentielle Erosionsgefährdung der Ackerböden durch Wind in Deutschland 1:100.000” shows regional hot-spots of potential soil erosion in Germany for arable soils. The method to predict the soil erosion risk (DIN 19706:2002 and documentation of AG Boden) was adapted by the BGR based on the soil texture (BÜK1000N), the mean annual wind speed at 10 m height in 1981-2000 (DWD) and land use information from CORINE Land Cover dataset 2006 (UBA/DRL) (Bug, 2014b).

Validity The map shows a potential erosion situation without consideration of wind obstacles and cultivated crops and assuming arable land use with a crop that

poorly covers the soil. The method is based on DIN 19706:2013-02.

Access The map is provided without registration and free of charge at the [Produktcenter](#) of the BGR in the formats GeoTIFF, TIFF, PNG and PDF.

GeoTIFF-URL:
https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/pegwind1000/pdf/pegwind1000_250_v10.zip
 WMS-URL: <https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/pegwind1000/>

2.4.9	Soil erosion risk through water for Germany	Germany	UBA	2011	Raster	1 km
Description	The map “Erosionsgefährdung landwirtschaftlicher Böden durch Wasser in Deutschland” is a product of a study which was initiated by the UBA to examine the impacts of climate change on soil erosion by water with focus on the usage-based erosion potential in German agricultural areas. The estimation follows an USLE approach for calculating the R-Factor, implemented in ABAGFlux and TerraFlux. The climate data are based on the statistical climate model WETTREG which is related to the global model ECHAM5/MPI-OM for the emission scenario A1B (Wurbs and Steininger, 2011).					
Validity	The climate scenarios which are generally used in Germany (STAR, REMO, CLM, WETTREG) show very different results concerning the precipitation estimation. The model result is valid for the small scale estimation. For local and large scale analysis the model is inadvisable and it was recommended to use approaches of the federal state offices (e.g. the KLIWA concept study for Bavaria, Baden-Wuerttemberg and Rhineland-Palatinate) (Wurbs and Steininger, 2011).					
Access	The model result has to be requested at the UBA and is not described by metadata.					

2.4.10	Soil erosion risk through wind for Germany	Germany	UBA	2017	Raster	1 km
Description	The two maps (natural and potential soil erosion risk) are products of a study which was initiated by the Federal Environmental Agency (UBA) called “Ausmaß und Prognose der Winderosion auf ackerbaulich genutzten Böden in Deutschland (UFOPLAN – FKZ 371371231)”. The soil erosion by wind was estimated in accordance with DIN 19706:2013-02. The input data are BÜK1000N (BGR), ATKIS-DLM (BKG), mean annual wind speed in 10 m height 1981-2000 (DWD) and frequency of the 8 main wind directions (wind speed > 7m/s) (DWD). The raster maps visualize the natural erosion risk in six threat classes.					
Validity	For local and large scale analysis the map product is not suitable due to (Steininger and Wurbs, 2017): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - aggregation of the crop information at natural landscapes level - soil association in the soil units of the BÜK1000N leads to spatial leveling Further methodological limitations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no of consideration of soil tillage and soil moisture in DIN 19706 - no of differentiation of wind frequency and land cover during the course of one year in DIN 19706 - classification of silt soils in the DIN scheme leads to underestimation of the natural erosion risk, especially on the loess soils of East Germany 					
Supplement	UBA, 2017b					
Access	The model result has to be requested at the UBA and is not described by metadata.					

2.4.11	Soil erosion in Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m
Description	<p>The map is a product of the application of the general soil erosion equation (<i>Allgemeine Bodenabtragungsgleichung – ABAG</i>) and provides a nationwide overview of the individual erosion factors (C, K, L R, S) and the long-term average soil erosion. Data sources are the Main Land use Survey (“<i>Bodennutzungshaupterhebung</i>”) 2007 at the municipality scale, areas of catch crop cultivation and strip-till in 2010 at the scale of the local sub-districts (<i>Gemarkung</i>), values of the German soil taxation per parcel, DEM5 (grouped, per parcel).</p> <p>The map is derived of the soil map 1:50,000 BK50 for Baden-Wuerttemberg within the program <i>Integrierte Geowissenschaftliche Landesaufnahme</i> (GeoLa).</p>					
Completeness	<p>Information about the methods used is available in the metadata description of the LGRB-map viewer, but these are incomplete (no information about the climate data used here). These deviate from the information given in a short publication of the LGRB (2013).</p>					
Resolution	<p>The data bases used for the map have differ in their spatial resolution from 5 m (DEM5) up to municipality-level (land use data).</p>					
Access	<p>The map can be displayed in the LGRB-map viewer (http://maps.lgrb-bw.de/?view=lgrb_bodenerosion) or downloaded as WMS. The SHAPE-file of the dataset is not freely available.</p> <p>WMS-URL: http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_bodenerosion</p>					

2.4.12	Soil erosion risk for soils in Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1: 300,000
Description	<p>Important parameters for the evaluation of erosion risk by wind and water are the field block and the benchmark index (“<i>Vergleichsindex</i>”). Each field block receives a population-based assessment of erosion risk (0 = no to 100 = maximum). Forest and settlement areas are not included.</p>					
Validity	<p>The erosion is calculated according to the general soil erosion equation (ABAG) (LBGR, 2017c).</p>					
Access	<p>WMS-URL http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/boerosion_wms? WFS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/boerosion_wfs?</p>					

2.4.13	Erodibility of the topsoil for North Rhine-Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	The map "Erodierbarkeit des Oberbodens" was derived from the soil map 1:50,000 for North-Rhine Westfalia (GD-NW, 2016).					
Completeness	The map is complete except small residual areas in the border area to the neighboring state Lower Saxony.					
Currentness	On 2018-03-15 the service was extensively updated.					
Access	The data are available in one layer set with the soil map as WMS and AtomFeed/SHAPE via the Geoportal.NRW and the Geological Survey GD-NW (Download service: www.tim-online.nrw.de). License: dl-de/by-2-0. WMS-URL: https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk050? AtomFeed: https://www.gis-rest.nrw.de/atomFeed/rest/atom/5c120c49-1486-4fc0-827c-da14624af4a4 SHAPE- URL: https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK50/ISBK50_EPSG25832_Shape.zip					

2.4.14	Potential erosion risk of the arable land of Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LBG-RLP	2017	Polygon	1:5,000
Description	The potential erosion risk of the arable land ('Wassererosionsgefährdungsklasse Cross Compliance') was determined in the course of the preparation of the Saarland erosion protection ordinance and is derived from data of the soil estimation, the slope and slope length as well as precipitation data. The Draft Direct Payments Obligations Regulation provides for a classification of these areas into erosion risk classes. GRID_CODE 1 = erosion risk due to precipitation (designation in the legend in the geoportal: CCW1) GRID_CODE 2 = high risk of erosion due to precipitation (designation in the legend in the geoportal: CCW2) (CCW = water cross-compliance requirements). The digital map consists of vector shapes. A map for potential soil erosion risk is available also at the scale of 1:50,000 in the dataset 'Schutzwürdige und schutzbedürftige Böden'.					
Validity	Calculation based on DIN 19708 (LGB, 2010).					
Access	The WMS and the WFS (http://www.geoportal.rlp.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=1764&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS) is accessible via Geoportal.rlp and via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client (CC BY-NC 3.0).					

2.4.15	Water erosion risk for agricultural areas (CCW SL WMS), Saarland	DE-SL	LVGL-SL	2018	Polygon	1:100,000
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Description The potential erosion risk of the Saarland arable land was determined in the course of the preparation of the Saarland erosion protection ordinance and is derived from data of the soil estimation, the slope and slope length as well as precipitation data. The Draft Direct Payments Obligations Regulation provides for a classification of these areas into erosion risk classes. GRID_CODE 1 = erosion risk due to precipitation (designation in the legend in the geoportal: CCW1) GRID_CODE 2 = high risk of erosion due to precipitation (designation in the legend in the geoportal: CCW2) (CCW = water cross-compliance requirements) (LVGL-SL, 2018).

Validity Calculation is based on DIN 19708.

Access Viewing within the online-applications of the LVGL or within GeoPortal.Saarland is free of charge. Any further utilization, such as embedding in other applications (download) is subject to fee and requires a contractual agreement.

WMS-URL:

http://geoportal.saarland.de/mapbender/php/wms.php?layer_id=31251&PHPSESID=dce4708b1d612c7122a3c6f993eee857&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE=WMS

2.4.16	Map of erosion risk for Saxonian soils	DE-SN	LfULG	2013	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description The map shows the two layers 'Erosion-prone steep slopes / *Erosionsgefährdete Steillagen*' and 'Erosion-prone drainage paths/ *Erosionsgefährdete Abflussbahnen*'. The following data sources were included in the present map: BK50 (LfULG, 2012), DEM5 (generalized from DEM2 (GeoSN, 2012)) and precipitation series from 1993 to 2012 (DWD, 2013).

Access The dataset is provided free of charge in SHAPE-format after request via the download service (<https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/boden/27787.htm>). The WFS is freely accessible via the Geoportal.Sachsenatlas: https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/infosysteme/wfs/services/boden/erosion_utm/MapServer/WFSServer?

2.5 Soil Carbon and Organic Matter Content

2.5.1	Global Soil Organic Carbon Map (GSOCmap)	Global	FAO	2017	Raster	1 km
Description	The GSOCmap is the first map product published by GLOIS and the first global soil organic carbon map produced through a consultative and participatory process involving member countries of the Global Soil Partnership (FAO and ITPS, 2018).					
Currentness	The GSOCmap is to be continuously improved as the countries gather more data to improve their maps within a versioning system (FAO and ITPS, 2018).					
Validity	The map is being compiled from national maps and generated using existing soil profile data and soil polygon maps. So, the data quality depends strongly on the quality of the national databases.					
Access	The map is available online via web map application allowing to view, query and download the data (GeoTIFF), including the metadata acknowledging all organizations which contributed to the map (http://54.229.242.119/GSOCmap/).					

2.5.2	Soil Organic Carbon - Saturation Capacity	EU28	JRC	2016	Raster	250 m
Description	This dataset (map) shows the Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) saturation capacity, expressed as the ratio between the actual (derived from the Pan-European simulation using the biogeochemical CENTURY model) and the potential (scenario: grassland land use without nitrogen limitation) SOC stock in each pixel. Values close to 0 indicate a great potential of soil to store more carbon.					
Completeness	Coverage: EU + Balkan + Norway. The simulation of the potential SOC stock involved only the agricultural soils, according to the CORINE Land Cover.					
Access	The dataset is a single ESRI Grid in the ETRS_LAEA_10_52 Coordinate System + the two referenced articles (Lugato et al., 2013; Lugato et al., 2014). To get access to the data, the user must compile the online request form of the ESDAC portal . https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-organic-carbon-saturation-capacity					

2.5.3	CENTURY – pan-European baseline for SOC	Europe	JRC	2014	Polygon	-
Description	<p>The maps are a product of the agro-ecosystem SOC model CENTURY which was applied in the CAPRESE project (Carbon PREservation and SEquestration in agricultural soils). The dataset of the ESDAC includes the maps "Pan-European SOC stock of agricultural soils" (vector), "Potential carbon sequestration by modelling a comprehensive set of management practices" (raster) and "Average Eroded SOC in agricultural soils" (raster). The model projected Soil Organic Carbon baseline content (t C ha⁻¹ in 0-30 cm depth) of the arable land use, where the following alternative management practices (AMP) are applied: conversion from arable to grassland (AR_GR_LUC); crop residue management (AR_RES); reduced tillage (AR_RT); crop residue + reduced tillage (AR_RET); ley in rotation (AR_LEY); cover crops (AR_CC). The projection is based on derived data from official statistics for the main management practices. The model results were tested against approximately 20,000 soil samples from the 2009 LUCAS topsoil survey (Lugato et al., 2013; Lugato et al., 2014).</p>					
Validity	<p>The output from the CENTURY model showed mainly a good overlap with the measured values of the LUCAS survey but with regional variances, e.g. higher uncertainties on sandy soils. For Germany the uncertainty of the model was about 20-40 % (Lugato, et al., 2013).</p>					
Access	<p>The products of the model are available after request at the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) including "Pan-European SOC stock of agricultural soils" (polygon in Shape format), "Potential carbon sequestration by modelling a comprehensive set of management practices" (1 x 1 km raster in GeoTIFF format) and "Average Eroded SOC in agricultural soils" (1 x 1 km raster in GeoTIFF format). The most recent version of the top-soil SOC stock based on modelling updates is available as 1 x 1 km raster at the ESDAC: "Erosion integration in the European Carbon balance - Soil organic carbon content of agricultural soils of EU" for the year 2010 (Lugato et al., 2015).</p>					

2.5.4	Variations in topsoil organic carbon content across Europe	Europe	JRC/ EEA	2010	Raster	1 km
Description	<p>The map is based on data from 2003 and shows seven classes of the percentage of organic carbon content in the surface horizon of soils in Europe.</p>					
Reusability	<p>The map is only available as image and not in geodata format.</p>					
Access	<p>The map is free for download (EEA standard reuse policy, equal to CC BY 3.0) at the EEA database in GIF, TIFF, PNG, and Postscript-file format (.esp). https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/variations-in-topsoil-organic-carbon</p>					

2.5.5	Predicted distribution of SOC content in Europe (SoilTrEC project)	EU28	JRC/EEA	2016	Raster/point	1 km
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Description The map shows the predicted distribution of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) content in Europe in 2016. The prediction is based on aggregated 23,835 soil samples collected from the LUCAS Project (agricultural soil), BioSoil Project (forest soil), and “Soil Transformations in European Catchments” (SoilTrEC) Project (local soil data from critical zone observatories) as well as 15 spatial indicators (Aksoy et al., 2016).

Completeness The availability of samples for agricultural sites (19,860 samples) was much better in comparison to forest sites.

Access The access is provided free of charge via the [ESDAC](https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/predicted-distribution-soc-content-europe-based-lucas-bio-soil-and-czo-context-eu-funded-1) but has to be requested with an online request form (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/predicted-distribution-soc-content-europe-based-lucas-bio-soil-and-czo-context-eu-funded-1>).

2.5.6	Organic matter content of top-soils	Germany	BGR	2007	Polygon	1:1,000,000
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Description The map “Gehalte an organischer Substanz in Oberböden Deutschlands” is based on the results of a compilation of typical soil organic matter contents in top-soils in Germany differentiated according to 15 groups of soil parent material, four climatic areas and the main land use (Stange, 2007). The classes of the map legend are based on the classes given in the German Soil Survey Guideline (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The map product is based on more than 9,000 soil profiles sampled in a period of about 20 years. Detailed information about Methods are documented in a report (BGR, 2007).

Validity The mean number of strata per 100 km² is 3, which limits the spatial representation.

Access SHAPE-
URL: https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/HUMUS1000OB/shp/humus1000_ob_v20.zip
WMS-URL: <https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/humus1000ob/>

2.5.7	Organic carbon in the soils for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	50 m
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Description The C_{org} contents and stocks of soils in Baden-Württemberg are calculated here to a depth of 100 cm below ground by multiple linear regressions taking into account climate, soil and relief parameters separated by land use and soil type groups.

Access The map can be displayed in the LGRB-map viewer or downloaded as WMS:
http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?SERVICE=WMS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_corg

2.5.8	C _{org} -content in soil for Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1:300,000
Description	Humus content classes in the topsoil in 0.3 m, 1 m and 2 m below surface were classified according with the German Soil Survey Guideline, 5 th Ed., tab. 15 (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The map is based on the legend units of the soil map (BÜK300). The single (areal) soil forms were combined with parameters, including the corresponding C _{org} levels which were determined by terrain and laboratory tests. Areas with the same horizon-substrate combinations have been merged and the specific parameters (such as levels of C _{org}) have been derived statistically (median). The succession of horizon-substrate combinations of areal soil forms and the C _{org} content formed the basis for the calculation of the amounts in t/ha. These were classified in levels of 30 t / ha (LBGR, 2017d).					
Completeness	Data on carbon content are not yet available in this service and will be added later.					
Resolution	The map is not suitable for visualizations in a scale larger than 1:100,000.					
Access	WMS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bohumuskohl_wms? WFS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/bohumuskohl_wfs?					

2.5.9	Carbon content of the subsoil (BTOC50) for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2014	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	The map visualizes the Total Organic Carbon (TOC) content of the subsoil (80-130 cm and 130-200 cm) for arable areas in Lower Saxony based on a regional soil carbon model (see Möller and Kennepohl, 2014). The source for the carbon data is the NIBIS-laboratory database and the base profiles (<i>Leitprofile</i>) of the map BÜK50. These data were					
Validity	The validity of the derived data is lower for the deeper soil horizons due to a lack of data for the deeper subsoil. Single soil types (marshland and peat soils) can be described only with a high uncertainty. A future edition of the dataset based on the more detailed BK50 will increase the prediction accuracy (Möller and Kennepohl, 2014).					
Supplement	Very detailed information about the methods are published by Möller and Kennepohl (2014).					
Access	The dataset is not freely available. The map is visualized in the <i>NIBIS-Kartenserver</i> were the WMS-URL is published: http://nibis.lbeg.de/net3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=901&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&					

2.6 Input and Flow of Nutrients and Substances

2.6.1	Global assessment of soil phosphorus retention potential	Global	Batjes, N. H.	2016	Raster	30"
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Description	Derived values for pH, soil mineralogy, and clay content were used to rate the capacity for P retention of the component soil units of each map unit (or grid-cell) using four classes (i.e., Low, Moderate, High, and Very High) (Batjes, 2016).
Validity	Uncertainties remain high (Batjes, 2011).
Access	The data can be downloaded via the dataportal PANGAEA under consideration of CC BY 3.0: https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.858549 .

2.6.2	DayCent model - N ₂ O emissions from agricultural soils in Europe	Europe	JRC	2017	DBF	1 km
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Description	This dataset is based on the LUCAS soil survey data in combination with the biogeochemistry process-based model DayCent. The model was run for more than 11,000 LUCAS sampling points under agricultural use and contains the average (2010-2014 time period) emissions of N ₂ O-N (kg/ha/yr). The model outcome upscales the N ₂ O emissions at 1 km resolution.
Supplement	Detailed information is published in Lugato et al. 2017 https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0176111 .
Validity	Two types of data were used: 1) LUCAS point data without an uncertainty range and 2) information from official statistics (NUTS2) with uncertainty analysis. The LUCAS survey does not provide information about agricultural management practices, therefore conventional agro-techniques were assumed for all areas. This results in high uncertainties of the model input. "Even though DayCent is one of the most used process-based models for estimating N ₂ O fluxes, calibration of the model at experimental field sites in Europe is scarce and the model-bias is therefore largely unknown." (Lugato et al., 2017, p. 13/16).
Access	The access is provided free of charge via the ESDAC but has to be requested with an online request form. The average nitrous oxides emissions are available in DBF-format and can be joined with the LUCAS soil properties SHAPE (field 'sample_ID'). The upscaled raster data are available in GeoTIFF format. https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/n2o-emissions-agricultural-soils

2.6.3	Maps of the Storing and Filtering Capacity of the Soils in Europe	Europe	JRC	2015	Polygon/ Raster	1:1,000,000 1 km
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Description The maps for the area of 27 EU member states were derived in the frame of a study to estimate and map the soil filtering and storing capacity of different substances (Makó et al., 2017). The results are based on LUCAS topsoil data (organic carbon, see record [1.1.4](#)), the European Soil Database (texture, slope, topsoil organic carbon, peat, volume of stones, topsoil packing density, effective soil depth), the Pedotransfer Rules database, the CORINE Land Cover database 2006, the FAO's World Reference Base for Soil Resources (humus quality, depth to groundwater) and the BGR's map "Soil regions of the European Union and Adjacent Countries 1:5,000,000" v.2.0 2005 (agro-climatic zones). The parameters are converted in a ten-step scale ranging from "poor" (1) to good" (10) by using the Visual Binning method (equal number of cases per category).

- cation storing capacity
- cation filtering capacity
- anion storing capacity
- anion filtering capacity
- solids and pathogenic microorganisms storing capacity
- solids and pathogenic microorganisms filtering capacity
- non-polar organic chemicals storing capacity
- non-polar organic chemicals filtering capacity
- nonaqueous Phase Liquids (NAPL) storing capacity
- nonaqueous Phase Liquids (NAPL) filtering capacity

Supplementary The methodological procedures is described in detail by Makó et al. (2017).

Access To get access to the data, the user has to compile the online request form of the [ESDAC portal](#). There are two data set versions available: the ten maps compiled in one SHAPE file or the ten maps plus intermediate parameters. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/maps-storing-and-filtering-capacity-soils-europe>

2.6.4	Soil substances	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m
Description	<p>In Germany the concept of background values (Hintergrundwerte) was established to estimate the amount of inorganic trace substances in the soil (LABO, 2003). The map product „Stoffe in Böden in Deutschland“ shows grouped background values (90-percentile) of the following trace elements for the topsoil, the subsoil and the bedrock: arsenic, beryllium, cadmium, cobalt, copper, mercury, molybdenum, nickel, lead, stibium, selenium, thallium, uranium, vanadium, zinc. A project by the BGR (F+E „Fortschreibung bundesweiter Hintergrundwerte für anorganische Stoffe in Böden“ 2012-16) joined the background values of the federal states in one dataset for 13 bedrock types in the topsoil, subsoil and ground (Stange et al., 2015). The theme maps are derived by using the BÜK1000N (BGR), the DEM50 (BKG), climatic information of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) for the period 1961-1990 as well as on land use data from the dataset CORINE Land Cover 2006 (UBA).</p>					
Completeness	<p>The datasets coverage is limited to areas in Germany under agricultural land use in 2006.</p>					
Validity	<p>The density of measurement points is very different from one federal state to another, so the database includes only points with a minimum distance of 999 m. This thinning has an influence on the derived background value for some heavy metals (Stange et al., 2015).</p>					
Access	<p>The maps are provided without registration and free of charge at the Produktcenter of the BGR via WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/bodenstoffe/?</p>					

2.6.5	Nitrogen and Sulphur deposition for Germany (PINETI-model)	Germany	UBA	2017	Raster	250 m
Description	<p>The German Environmental Agency (UBA) presents interactive maps of spatial consistent nitrogen deposition for Germany with a resolution of 1 x 1 km² and with linkage to land use classes. The maps are based on data of the UBA-Project PINETI (Pollutant INput and EcosysTem Impact) as a product of combined modelled and measured values of the total nitrogen and sulphur deposition (Wichink Kruit et al., 2014). Dry, wet and humid deposition of NH_x, NO_y, SO_x and the base cations Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺ und Na⁺ are calculated and added up to the total deposition (Schaap et al., 2017; Schaap et al., 2018). The most current model PINETI-3 is an improved version with long-term consistent time series analysis (2000-2015, while PINETI-2 uses 2009 as representative year), consideration of the compensation point, consideration of cloud deposition and improved data availability (Schaap et al., 2018). The results are used to calculate the exceedance of critical loads for future emissions scenarios and international programs (“International Cooperative Programme on Modelling and Mapping of Critical Levels & Loads and Air Pollution Effects, Risks and Trends“ (ICP M&M)). Some State Offices do not use the UBA-Model and express doubts in its representativeness and precision, e.g. LUBW Baden-Wuerttemberg uses own models based on the through fall measurement/canopy budget models (<i>Kronenraumbilanzmessung</i>).</p> <p>The PINETI-3 dataset consists of the following data: mean value (2013-2015) of total N-deposition for 10 land use classes, mean values and single years (2013, 2014, 2015) of the nitrogen fluxes (dry, wet, humid, total) for NH_x, NO_y and N-total for 10 land use classes.</p>					

Completeness	<p>The model PINETI-3 uses data from about 300 stations of the states' measurement net but with un-regular geographical coverage and gaps in Brandenburg, Mecklenburg Western-Pomerania and North Rhine-Westphalia.</p> <p>The dry deposition is modelled with the LOTOS-EUROS model. GRETA (Gridding Emission Tool for ArcGIS) is an emission model which is integrated in LOTOS-EUROS. GRETA uses data from the Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (www.thru.de) but with gaps in the emission data from livestock farming due to missing registration or difficult availability or no legal obligation for registration (e.g. for cowsheds).</p>
Currentness	<p>In 2018 the current deposition model PINETI-2 was substituted by the improved model PINETI-3 which uses time series data for the years 2000-2015 instead of one reference year and includes methodological improvements.</p>
Validity	<p>PINETI-2 was characterized by overestimations of the modelled deposition values in comparison with observed local values. PINETI-3 matches the actual measured values much better. However, very local emission sources or orographic characteristics are not represented in the model.</p>
Supplement	<p>A collection of FAQs and answers to questions that were addressed to the UBA in an expert discussion on October 24, 2017 in Dessau was published online: http://gis.uba.de/website/depo1/download/Erlaeuterungen_DepoKartendienst_UBA_PINETI3.pdf</p>
Access	<p>The model results for the years 2013-2015 are provided via web map application: http://gis.uba.de/website/depo1/. The data are available free of charges after signing a user agreement with the UBA (Section II 4.3, available in PDF-format via the map application interface) in ASCII-format for 2013, 2014 and 2015. Results of the former model version PINET-2 for the years 2009, 2010 and 2011 can be requested at the UBA. The Station Database of the UBA contains all information about the stations including information about the measurement configuration of the immission observation stations of the states (https://www.env-it.de/stationen/public/language.do?language=en).</p>

2.6.6	Relative binding strength for heavy metals in Brandenburg	DE-BB	LBGR	2017	Polygon	1:300,000
Description	<p>Relative binding strength for heavy metals for the three depth ranges a) topsoil, b) up to 1 m tread depth and c) groundwater-free ground space in the state of Brandenburg. Al, Pb, Cd, Cr (III), Fe (III), Co, Cu, Mn, Ni, Hg and Zn. Based on the legend units of the soil map (BÜK300) with assignment of corresponding areal soil forms. For this purpose, the corresponding parameters (soil type, humus content, pH value) were statistically derived for the same horizon-substrate combinations (usually the median value) (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2000).</p>					
Access	<p>WMS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/boschworm_wms? WFS-URL: http://inspire.brandenburg.de/services/boschworm_wfs?</p>					

2.6.7	Potential risk for nitrate leaching on arable areas in Mecklenburg-W Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000
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Description The map “Potentielle Nitratauswaschungsgefährdung” in the winter season is processed according to method 5.1 of the *Methodendokumentation Bodenkunde* (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2000).
The land use type (ATKIS) with the largest area was assigned to each unit of the soil map ‘Konzeptbodenkarte’ 1:25,000 (KBK25) (LUNG, 2010). The result distinguishes five classes of worthiness of protection from lowest to highest worthiness.

Access Available for visualization via the *Umweltkarten* geoportal for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and as WFS via the MetaVer-catalogue:
https://www.umweltkarten.mv-regierung.de/script/mv_a7_bodengeologie_wfs.php?

2.6.8	Derived maps based on the soil map BK50 for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2018	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description A number of maps were processed based on the Lower Saxonian soil map 1:50,000 (BK50):

- a) “Austauschhäufigkeit des Bodenwassers” – exchange frequency of soil water (per year), in five classes.
- b) “Relative Bindungsstärke des Bodenwassers für Schwermetalle – Cadmium” – relative binding strength for heavy metals – cadmium. For details about the derivation procedure see Müller and Waldeck (2011).
- c) “Effektive Durchwurzelungstiefe des Bodens” - Effective Rooting Depth of the Soil: The map shows the size of the root area in dm, classified in 6 stages. The effective rooting depth depends on the texture, the storage density, the humus content, the stratification and the use of the soil as well as the groundwater level (Müller and Waldeck, 2011).

Validity The methodological description in publication by Müller and Waldeck (2011) differs from the metadata description of the dataset.

Access The map layer is available as WMS at the *NIBIS-Kartenserver* of the LBEG. The attributed note box provides an URL for the WMS:

- a) <http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodId=1023&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&>
- b) <http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodId=1021&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&>
- c) <https://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodId=1000&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&>

2.6.9	Denitrification potential of the soil (BÜK50) in Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2015	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The denitrification potential is derived up to the depth of 2 m under the use of the Lower Saxonian soil map 1:50,000 (BÜK50). Each type of soil is assigned a denitrification level at a mean annual rate, depending on the influence by groundwater or waterlogging. This was processed by a modification of the estimation method according to Gäth et al. (1997) (Wienhaus et al., 2008). The layer presents five denitrification classes, which are characterized by the mean denitrification rates of 5, 20, 40, 60 and 100 kg N/ha*a (in peat-dominated substrates 150 kg N/ha*a) (LBEG, 2016).
Access	The map layer is available in WMS at the NIBIS Map server of the State Office for Mining, Energy and Geology (LBEG) Lower Saxony. The layer can be selected in the theme-tree and the attributed note box provides an URL for the WMS, a legend and a description (German).

2.6.10	Denitrification potential of the soil (IS BK 50) for North-Rhine Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	The map "Denitrifikationspotential" was derived from the soil map 1:50,000 for North-Rhine Westphalia (GD-NW, 2016).
Completeness	The map is complete except small residual areas in the border area to the neighboring state Lower Saxony.
Currentness	On 2018-03-15 the service was extensively updated.
Reusability	Detailed description of the data processing methods and data sources are not part of the metadata. This information is provided online at the website of the GD-NW: https://www.gd.nrw.de/pr_shop_informationssysteme_bk50d.htm .
Access	The dataset is INSPIRE-identified and available in one layer set with the soil map as WMS and AtomFeed/ SHAPE via the Geoportal.NRW and the Geological Survey GD-NW (Download service: www.tim-online.nrw.de). License: dl-de/by-2-0. WMS-URL: https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk050? AtomFeed: https://www.gis-rest.nrw.de/atomFeed/rest/atom/5c120c49-1486-4fc0-827c-da14624af4a4 SHAPE-URL: https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK50/ISBK50_E_PSG25832_Shape.zip

2.6.11	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200) for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	<p>The dataset “Schutzwürdige und schutzbedürftige Böden“ includes the following layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buffering capacity for acids • Retention capacity for lead • Retention capacity for cadmium • Leaching risk for water soluble substances • Buffering capacity for water soluble substances <p>Other maps of this dataset are described under record 2.14 and 6.15.</p>
Currentness	The methodology to assess the vulnerability of the soils corresponds to the five classes which were applied for other federal states.
Supplement	Detailed information about the single soil functions, their parameter, processed data and methods are provided in a comprehensive report (MUF, 2005).
Access	<p>The WMS and the WFS for each layer are accessible via Geoportal.rlp and via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client (CC BY-NC 3.0).</p> <p>WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd50_200?</p> <p>WFS-URL: http://www.geoportal.rlp.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=1741&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS</p>

2.6.12	Nitrate retention capacity (BÜK200) for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2002	Polygon	1:200,000
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Description	The map was derived based on the soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200) for Rhineland-Palatinate. Input data: risk for mineralization, potential for dry cracks development, field capacity, potential for back water influence (Friedrich and Vorderbrügge, 2002).
Currentness	New derived maps of the soil map 1:200,000 (BÜK200) for Germany published by the BGR will be available in the next future.
Access	<p>The data are listed in the catalogue of the Geoportal.de and can be visualized via the WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd200?</p>

2.6.13	Nitrate retention capacity, Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000
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Description	The map “Nitratrückhaltevermögen” is based on the soil map of the Saarland BÜK100 and physical parameters of the states’ profile database of the soil information system SAARBIS. The used parameters are field capacity in the rooting zone, water retention capacity, the tendency to form dry cracks and mineralization potential of the organic substrate (LUA, 2009).
Supplement	A detailed report was published by the LUA (2009).
Access	<p>A WMS including a set of layers is accessible via INSPIRE, via the Geoportal of the Saarland and the Geoportal.de. The reuse is free under consideration of the LVGL-User license. WMS-URL: http://geoportal.saarland.de/arcgis/services/Internet/Boden_Internet/MapServer/WmsServer?</p>

2.6.14	Background values of the topsoil, Saxony-Anhalt	DE-ST	LAGB	2014	Polygon	1:200,000
Description	The map visualizes the inorganic background values of substances in the topsoil for the 50th percentile (median) and 90th percentile, respectively, based on the soil map 1:200,000. The data were sampled in a number of survey programs (e.g. long-term soil monitoring) since 1991. Additional parameters for all samples are grain size distributions, pH value and, if necessary, the humus content and CaCO ₃ . The procedure is based on the concept that characteristics of horizon groups of the same substrates do not differ significantly in their chemical and physical properties ("Substrat-Horizont-Gruppen" Vetterlein, 1986) (LAGB, 2006; LAGB, 2014). The data are grouped in five classes for the map.					
Validity	The measurements made at reference sites show matching values according to the different methods (LAGB, 2014).					
Supplement	Detailed information about the methods are published in a report (LAGB, 2014).					
Access	The dataset is INSPIRE-identified and provided for visualization via WMS-URL: https://www.geodatenportal.sachsen-anhalt.de/gfds/ws/wms/94e9d9fd-7776-5ed6/GDI-LSA_LAGB_BUEK200_HGW/ows.wms?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WMS					

For Saxony the LfULG has been operating a nitrate monitoring network since 1990, which annually comprises approx. 1,000 permanently measured permanent test areas (DTF) at farm sites (LfULG, 2016). The results are presented without detailed geospatial relation.

2.7 Soil Management and Soil Functional Datasets

The main source for biomass production and agricultural management data are the official agricultural survey programs like the Agricultural Census and the Farm Structure Survey. Here the accessibility for data at the large scale (e.g. farm level or municipality) is restricted.

Several German federal states already derived soil function maps in the late 1990th, but with different methodological schemes. Therefore, the Geological Surveys of the federal states developed a catalogue of methods for the derivation of soil functions and soil function maps (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2007). This catalogue includes further an overview of the single parameters used by the states' institutions.

2.7.1	Agricultural Census 2010	EU28	JRC/ Destatis	2017	Table	NUTS2/ NUTS3
Description	Every ten years, a full scope survey is carried out in the form of an agricultural census.					
Currentness	Methodological changes are expected for the next census. Eurostat's programme for the modernisation of agricultural statistics in the EU (Strategy for Agricultural Statistics for 2020 and beyond) was launched in 2016 and is still in progress.					
Supplement	The methodology is described in detail in a report (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2010).					
Access	The results are published in the German regional data base 'Regionaldatenbank Deutschland' for NUTS1, NUTS2 and NUTS3 level. The Eurostat public database published the EU level, country level and NUTS2 level. Data at a larger scale are managed by the Forschungsdatenzentrum Nord and are accessible with restrictions concerning the privacy issues of the farmers. https://www.regionalstatistik.de/genesis/online/data					

2.7.2	Farm Structure Survey 2016	EU28	JRC/ Destatis	2018	Table	NUTS2/ NUTS3
Description	Every 2 or 3 years, between the Agricultural censuses (every 10 years), sample surveys of the Farm Structure Survey (FSS) are carried out. The most recent took place in 2016, but the most recent published data are from 2013. The FSS covers the land use, livestock, labour force, production methods, and standard output of the EU-28's agricultural holdings. The information collected in the farm structure survey covers land use, livestock numbers, rural development, management and farm labour input (including the age, gender and relationship to the holder of the agricultural holding). The survey data can be aggregated by different geographic levels (for member states, regions, and districts). The data can also be arranged by size class, area status, legal status of the holding, objective zone and farm type.					
Completeness	Since 2010, some methodological changes have been introduced in the FSS limiting comparability with previous survey years.					
Access	The results are published in the German regional data base 'Regionaldatenbank Deutschland' for NUTS1, NUTS2 and NUTS3. The Eurostat public database published the EU level, country level and NUTS2 level. Data at a larger scale are managed by the Forschungsdatenzentrum Nord and are accessible with restrictions concerning the privacy issues of the farmers. Results are also published in a report (Eurostat, 2017). https://www.regionalstatistik.de/genesis/online/data					

2.7.3	Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the EU	EU27	JRC	2016	Raster	1 km
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Description	The dataset consists of 3 GIS maps that indicate the soil biomass productivity of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the European Union (EU27) (Tóth et al., 2013b).
Validity	Calculated values (in floating point), as described in the paper, where scaled to scores in the range [0,10] showing the relative fertility of soils expressed in relative index values without unit.
Access	The GIS-maps (GeoTIFF) can be requested at the data portal of the ESDAC which provides also comprehensive information about the methodology. https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-biomass-productivity-maps-grasslands-and-pasture-croplands-and-forest-areas-european

2.7.4	European map of soil suitability to provide a platform for most human activities	EU28	JRC	2015	Raster	1 km
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Description	The map presents the suitability for human activities based on properties of the European Soil database (soil type, soil water regime, limitation to agricultural use, depth to rock, land use) and slope of the terrain. Suitability of a given soil is calculated based on its structural stability. The strength of the soil is considered in terms of resistance against compaction and shearing stress.
Validity	The data have been internally produced by JRC (Tóth and Hermann, 2015) but have not been submitted yet for peer-review.
Supplement	The data portal of the ESDAC provides comprehensive information about the methodology and references.
Access	The maps (Geo TIFF-format) can be requested free of charge at the ESDAC data portal . https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-map-soil-suitability-provide-platform-most-human-activities-eu28

2.7.5	Soil quality rating for cropland in Germany	Germany	BGR / ZALF	2013	Polygon	1:1,000,000
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Description	The Soil Quality Rating (SQR) was developed in 2013 by the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) in Muencheberg. SQR describes the suitability of sites under agricultural land use and helps to estimate the yield potential of sites at a global scale. This method was especially adapted for application with soil maps by the Federal Institute of Geosciences and Resources BGR and is published in the documentation of AG Boden (representing the soil experts of the federal Geological Surveys). The map shows the SQR for cropland in Germany based on the land use stratified soil map of Germany at scale 1:1,000,000 (BÜK1000N V2.31). Climate (DWD: reference period 1961-90), Relief (BKG: DGM250) and land use data (CLC2006) are used as input data in addition to the soil map. SQR consists of a series of pedotransfer rules. First, eight basic soil indicators are weighted and combined to describe the soil (texture, soil structure, aggregate size distrib., available water, potential rooting depth). These indicators are critical for farming and limit the overall soil quality. Only those hazard indicators were selected for SQR which have the greatest effect on potential grain yield. The final SQR-score ranges from about 0 to 102 points (Hennings, 2013; Mueller et al.,
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	2014).
Completeness	It only includes areas in Germany under agricultural land use in 2006.
Currentness	The Soil Quality Rating was processed one time in 2013 with no regular updating so far.
Access	The data are available at the Produktcenter of the BGR in the format PDF (600 dpi), GeoTIFF (https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/SQR1000/geotiff/sqr1000_250_v10.zip), JPEG (150 dpi), PNG (150 dpi), TIFF (300 dpi), WMS (OCQ: WMS 1.3.0) and analogue paper map.

2.7.6	Soil capability for Germany	Germany	BGR	2017	Raster	250 m
Description	The map product “Potenziale der Böden in Deutschland“ includes the Muencheberg Soil Quality Rating and maps for soil potential and soil threatening properties. The dataset of soil potentials offers layers with the assessment of the soil texture, humus stock, soil structure, bulk density of the deeper soil (‘Packungsdichte’), effective rooting depth, soil water availability, mean lowest groundwater level, slope, local soil quality (sum of all previously listed features). The dataset of soil threat indicators includes the assessment of acidification risk, ‘Gründigkeit’, drought risk, stone content in the root layer, factors for yield decline, indicator values for soil threats (BGR, 2017). The theme maps are based on BÜK1000N (BGR), the DEM50 (BKG), climatic information of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) for the period 1961-1990 as well as on land use data from the dataset CORINE Land Cover 2006 (UBA).					
Completeness	The datasets coverage is limited to areas in Germany under agricultural land use in 2006.					
Access	WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/bodenpotenziale/					

2.7.7	Soil Depth (rooting depth) in Germany	Germany	BGR	2015	Raster	250 m
Description	The map of the soil depth “Physiologische Gründigkeit der Böden Deutschlands“ shows the evaluation of the potential rooting depth of German soils. The map is derived from profile data of the BÜK1000N based on the KA5 standard (Ad-hoc AG Boden, 2005) and land use information of the CORINE Land Cover 2006 (UBA/DLR). The lower limit of a soil is bedrock or a groundwater influenced horizon (Bug, 2015a).					
Supplement	The methods are documented in the <i>MethodenWIKI Bodenkunde</i> of the FISBo BGR https://www.methodenwiki-bodenkunde.de					
Access	GeoTIFF- URL: https://download.bgr.de/bgr/Boden/PHYSGRU1000/geotiff/PhysGru1000_250.zip WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/physgru1000/					

2.7.8	Sensitivity of soils to compaction	Germany	BGR	2015	Raster	250 m
Description	The map shows the derived potential exposure of arable soil at a depth of 35 cm to soil compaction. The map is only valid at pF 1.8 and is derived from the BÜK1000N (Bug, 2015b).					
Validity	The ordinal scaled characteristic value is derived from the preloading of the soil.					
Access	GeoTIFF – URL: https://download.bgr.de/bgr/boden/LD1000/geotiff/LD1000_250.zip WMS-URL: https://services.bgr.de/wms/boden/ld1000/					

2.7.9	Derived soil function maps for Baden-Wuerttemberg	DE-BW	LGRB	2015	Raster	100 m
Description	Soil function maps are derived by the methods described by the LUBW (2010) based on the data of the GeoLa and the BK50 as well as the German soil taxation data. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural soil fertility (“Natürliche Bodenfruchtbarkeit”) • Site for semi-natural vegetation („Standort für naturnahe Vegetation“) • Compensator within the water cycle for arable areas/ forest (“Ausgleichskörper im Wasserkreislauf unter landwirtschaftlicher Nutzung/ unter Wald“) • Filter and buffer for pollutants for arable areas/ forest („Filter und Puffer für Schadstoffe unter landwirtschaftlicher Nutzung/ unter Wald“) • Possibility to dig 1 m deep in the soil („Grabbarkeit 1m“) • Total evaluation of the soil functions for arable area/ for forest 					
Validity	Only dominant soils with a share of >25 % of the total area are considered in the process (LGRB, 2012).					
Access	The data are a subject to charges. They are listed online under http://lgrb-bw.de/aufgaben_lgrb/geola/produkte_geola WMS-URL: http://services.lgrb-bw.de/index.phtml?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.1&SERVICE=WMS&SERVICE_NAME=lgrb_geola_bod					

2.7.10	Soil function maps for selected regions in Bavaria	DE-BY	LfU-BY	2017	Polygon	1:25,000
Description	The soil function maps are displayed in the "UmweltAtlas Bayern" in six different layers for Natural Yield Potential (‘Natürliche Ertragsfähigkeit’), Acid Buffering Capacity (‘Säurepuffervermögen’), Heavy Metal Retention (‘Schwermetallrückhalt’), Nitrate Retention Capacity (‘Nitratrückhaltevermögen’), Water Retention Capacity (‘Wasserretentionsvermögen’) and Site Potential for natural Vegetation (‘Standortpotential für natürliche Vegetation’). The assessment of the soil functions is based on soil maps (mainly ÜBK25) and other geographical information about the environmental and site conditions which were combined under consideration of specific rules. Each of the six layers for the different soil functional aspects is displayed in classes with six groups from very low to very high. The Site Potential for natural Vegetation is classified more detailed in accordance with the sites' conditions (LfU-BY, 2016).					

Completeness The soil function maps cover not the total area of the Bavarian state but large landscape units: The Upper Palatine-Bavarian Forest (Oberpfälzisch-Bayerischer Wald), Central Bavaria. The great variety of the basic data and maps (different topographical maps, raster data) result in intersection inaccuracies, especially for the intersection with current land use maps. Partly, the assessed areas are very inhomogeneous and beside the presented assessment classes divergent subordinated classes may occur. Areas with less than 5000 m² were merged with neighbouring areas.

Access The WMS is freely available (CC BY 3.0) but the vector data file with additional information (assessment of the soil function) is a subject to charges at the LfU-BY. For the overview map the LfU provides further model soil profiles with the main soil parameter information (water body size, carbonate content, cation exchange capacity, humus content, etc.).
<https://www.lfu.bayern.de/umweltdaten/datenbezug/index.htm>
 WMS-URL: <http://www.lfu.bayern.de/gdi/wms/boden/bfk25?>

2.7.11	Areal soil data for agricultural areas (BFD5L) for Hesse & Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-HE, DE-RP	HLNUG & LGB	2017	Polygon	1:5,000
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Description The BFD 5L was developed in the frame of the project ‘Bodenfunktionsbezogene Auswertung von Bodenschätzungsdaten’ in close cooperation with the HLNUG, the Regional Finance Office Koblenz, the LGB and the LVerGeo-RP and the *Ingenieurbüro Schnittstelle Boden*. As a basis, the data of the German soil taxation ([Bodenschätzung](#)) were used. The dataset includes a layer for soil texture types (aggregating 9 soil texture type groups), water conditions on grassland, field capacity, yield potential (‘Ackerzahl’), habitat typification and type of genesis. For detailed methodological information see the report (HLNUG, 2012). The scale of the layers ranges from 1:2,000 to 1:50,000.

Completeness In the present first version (version 1.3.0, 2017) of the MapServer only evaluations based on the class sign of the soil estimate are used. Further theme maps, e.g. the potential erosion risk from water or the location typing for the biotope development, will follow and be integrated into the MapServer after completion of the work.

Validity The database includes a software for plausibility check (syntax, semantics, conformity of the ‘Schätzungsbuch’ and the ‘Schätzungskarte’) (HLNUG and LGB, 2008).

Access The WMS is available without registration at the *Bodenviewer Hessen*. The datasets of the BFD5L are available for uncommercial use via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client as WFS.

WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd5?

WFS-URL:

http://www.geoportal.hessen.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=2383&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS

2.7.12	Soil function assessment maps for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania	DE-MV	LUNG	2017	Polygon	1:25,000
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Description	<p>The data background of the layers is the soil map 'Konzeptbodenkarte' 1:25,000 (KBK25) and the digital Basic-Landscape Model (LAIv).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural soil fertility ("natürliche Bodenfruchtbarkeit") • Extreme sites ("Extrem Standorte") • Semi-natural sites ("Naturnähe") <p>The result distinguishes five classes of worthiness of protection from lowest to highest worthiness.</p>
Supplement	A comprehensive documentation of the assessment process (LUNG, 2015) and a metadata description (LUNG, 2017b) were published online.
Access	Available for visualization via the <i>Umweltkarten</i> geoportal for Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and as WFS via the MetaVer-catalogue: https://www.umweltkarten.mv-regierung.de/script/mv_a7_bodengeologie_wfs.php?

2.7.13	Derived products based on the soil map BK50 for Lower Saxony	DE-NI	LBEG	2017	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	<p>A number of maps were processed based on the Lower Saxonian soil map 1:50,000 (BK50).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> „Gefährdung der Bodenfunktionen durch Bodenverdichtung“ (VDBF) - Threat of soil functions through soil compaction: The map product displays the threat of the soil functions up to 35 cm below ground through compaction by heavy machinery in five grades. The soil sensitivity towards compaction is derived related to the soil structure. Basic parameters are presented in Müller and Waldeck (2011). “Bodenfruchtbarkeit (Ertragspotenzial)” - Yield potential: The potential for biomass production is classified in 7 grades (very low – very high) based on the potential water and nutrients availability of the soil. Site-specific characteristics like slope or forest use were not considered (LBEG, 2018). “Standortabhängige Verdichtungsempfindlichkeit” - Location-dependent compaction sensitivity (VDST): The map shows the potential compaction sensitivity of the soil in 7 levels (very low- very high. The mentioned parameters are: soil texture, bulk density, humus content, soil moisture level, solidification and skeletal content (LBEG, 2017). The map has similarities with the map "Threat of soil functions through soil compaction".
Validity	The methodological description in the publication by Müller and Waldeck (2011) differs from the metadata description of the dataset.
Access	<p>The map layer is available as WMS at the <i>NIBIS-Kartenserver</i> of the LBEG. The attributed note box provides an URL for the WMS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=999&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=1017&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities& http://nibis.lbeg.de/cardomap3/public/ogc.ashx?NodeId=997&Service=WMS&Request=GetCapabilities&

2.7.14	Derived soil function maps based on the IS BK 50 for North-Rhine Westphalia	DE-NW	GD-NW	2016	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	<p>The following maps were derived from the soil map 1:50,000 for North-Rhine Westfalia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to dig in the soil (“Grabbarkeit”); • Value numbers of the German soil taxation (Bodenschätzung); • Sensible soils (“Schutzwürdigen Böden”); • Total filter effect; • Ecological moisture level (“Ökologische Feuchtestufen”); • leachate suitability (“Versickerungseignung”); • Sensitivity to soil compaction (“Verdichtungsempfindlichkeit“) (GD-NW, 2016). 					
Completeness	The map is complete except small residual areas in the border area to the neighboring state Lower Saxony.					
Currentness	On 2018-03-15 the service was extensively updated.					
Reusability	Detailed description of the data processing methods and data sources are not part of the metadata. The information is provided online at the website of the GD-NW: https://www.gd.nrw.de/pr_shop_informationssysteme_bk50d.htm .					
Access	<p>The data are INSPIRE-identified and available in one layer set with the soil map as WMS and AtomFeed/ SHAPE via the Geoportal.NRW and the Geological Survey GD-NW (Download service: www.tim-online.nrw.de). License: dl-de/by-2-0.</p> <p>WMS-URL: https://www.wms.nrw.de/gd/bk050?</p> <p>AtomFeed: https://www.gis-rest.nrw.de/atomFeed/rest/atom/5c120c49-1486-4fc0-827c-da14624af4a4</p> <p>SHAPE- URL: https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geologie/boden/BK/ISBK50/ISBK50_EPSG25832_Shape.zip</p>					

2.7.15	Vulnerable soils (BFD50/200) for Rhineland-Palatinate	DE-RP	LGB	2017	Polygon	1:50,000
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Description	<p>The dataset “Schutzwürdige und schutzbedürftige Böden“ includes the following layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural yield potential (“Natürliches Ertragspotential”) • Site potential for the development of habitats for extremely wet and dry soils (“Standortpotenzial für die Entwicklung von Biotopen extrem nasser und extrem trockener Böden“) • Soils as historico-cultural archives (“Böden als Archiv der Kultur- und Naturgeschichte“) <p>Other derived maps of this dataset were listed under record 2.14 and 5.10 in this report.</p>
Currentness	The methodology to assess the vulnerability of the soils corresponds to the five classes which were applied for other federal states.
Supplement	Detailed information about the single soil functions, their parameter, processed data and methods are provided in a comprehensive report (MUF, 2005).
Access	<p>The WMS and the WFS for each layer are accessible via Geoportal.rlp and via the INSPIRE ATOM Feed Client (CC BY-NC 3.0).</p> <p>WMS-URL: http://mapserver.lgb-rlp.de/cgi-bin/mc_bfd50_200?</p> <p>WFS-URL: http://www.geoportal.rlp.de/mapbender/php/wfs.php?INSPIRE=1&FEATURETYPE_ID=1741&request=GetCapabilities&VERSION=1.1.0&SERVICE=WFS</p>

2.7.16	Soil function maps (BÜK100), Saarland	DE-SL	LUA	2009	Polygon	1:100,000
Description	<p>Natural potential of cultivated soil:</p> <p>Classification of the yield potential according to the following classification: arable / grassland number 30 = very low, low = 30-39, 40-49 = medium, 50-59 = high, 59 = very high. The classes are adapted to the range of the Saarland soils.</p> <p>Map of site typing and habitat development potential of soils Depending on the water content and nutrient supply, the types of sites have a high to very high biotope development potential.</p> <p>Buffer areas of soils</p>					
Completeness	<p>Natural potential of cultivated soil: The geometry of the borders of the settlement and agricultural areas is outdated. Buffer areas: The database represents studies up to the year 1995, so that the acid entries of nearly two decades are disregarded. Current data is available for area-based studies and will be available later.</p>					
Access	<p>A WMS including a set of layers is accessible via INSPIRE, via the Geoportal of the Saarland and the Geoportal.de. All uses are free (CC BY 3.0). WMS-URL: http://geoportal.saarland.de/arcgis/services/Internet/Boden_Internet/MapServer/WmsServer?</p>					

2.7.17	Derived maps for soil protection and soil protection in Saxony	DE-SN	LfULG	2015	Polygon	1:50,000
Description	<p>The maps include the following layers with five evaluation classes (very low – very high):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural soil fertility (“Natürliche Bodenfruchtbarkeit”) • Water retention capacity (Wasserspeichervermögen“) • Filter and buffer for pollutants („Filter und Puffer für Schadstoffe“) • Cation exchange capacity („Kationenaustauschkapazität Wurzelraum“) • Air capacity („Luftkapazität im effektiven Wurzelraum“) • Erosion risk („Erodierbarkeit des Bodens – K-Faktor“) • Special site characteristics („Besondere Standorteigenschaften“) • Landscape-historical value („Landschaftsgeschichtliche Bedeutung“) <p>The derived data are processing results of the dominant profiles of the digital soil map BK50.</p>					
Validity	<p>The maps are derived based on standardized methods (LfULG, 2007; LfULG, 2009).</p>					
Reusability	<p>The LfULG provides comprehensive metadata.</p>					
Access	<p>The data are provided on DVD in SHAPE-format and MS ACCESS-Database which can be obtained via the LfULG, Ref.42 (remainders). The geodata infrastructure GEOMIS-Sachsen provides additionally the WMS: https://geoportal.umwelt.sachsen.de/arcgis/services/boden/bbw50/MapServer/WMServer? WFS-URL: http://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/infosysteme/wfs/services/boden/bbw50?</p>					

3. Conclusion

The accessibility and reusability of derived map products, e.g. for basic soil properties, hydrology, erosion and carbon, is generally high, both in raster and polygon formats. The main source for European-wide raster maps is the European Soil Data Centre and for global maps the SoilGrids products of the ISRIC-World Soil Information. The map products of the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR) are highly recommended for German-wide homogeneous soil maps, such as the Soil Map BÜK 200. The German federal State Geological Surveys provide soil maps with a higher resolution for visualization (WMS), but in the most cases without free access to the dataset. These regional soil maps differ strongly in the methodology applied for map production.

The accessibility of soil profile data and metadata is much more restricted compared to the map products which are based on them. The ESDAC provides survey data only for the upper soil layer (-30 cm). The soil profile data base of the BGR provides consistent profile information based on surveys of the federal states' surveys, but data usage is subject to individual agreements. The same use restrictions apply to the most recent profile data of the German Agricultural Soil Inventory (BZE-LW), which is also a valuable source for agricultural soil management data. The soil profile data bases of the federal states' surveys consist of data from several different survey programs and hold a rich data source, but their accessibility and reusability vary strongly, and only specific parts are published. One important and widely available part of these databases is the long-term field experiments data, with Germany-wide standardized methodology but different survey intervals.

The most critical issue regarding the soil data situation is the findability and accessibility of soil biological data. For Germany the main data sources are the soil-zoological data warehouse Edaphobase and data from long-term soil monitoring plots of the federal states. Geographical data on the distribution of soil microbial taxa (incl. OTUs) – such as provided by the French program Réseau de Mesure de la Qualité du Sol (RMQS) and the corresponding Atlas Bactéries du Sol - are currently not available for Germany.

Acronyms

ABAG	Allgemeine Boden-AbtragsGleichung/ General soil erosion equation
ALKIS	Amtliches Liegenschaftskatasterinformationssystem/ Official Real Estate Cadastre Information System for Germany
ATKIS	Amtliches Topographisch-Kartographisches Informationssystem/ Official Topographic Cartographic Information System for Germany
BfG	Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde/ The German Federal Institute of Hydrology: https://www.bafg.de
BGR	Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe/ Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources: https://www.bgr.bund.de
BKG	Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie/ Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy: https://www.bkg.bund.de
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst/ German Weather Service: https://www.dwd.de
EC	European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu
EC-JRC	European Union, represented by the European Commission, represented by the Directorate General-Joint Research Centre: https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en
EEA	European Environment Agency: https://www.eea.europa.eu
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre: https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu
Eurostat	Statistical Office of the European Union: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: http://www.fao.org
FZ Jülich	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH: http://www.fz-juelich.de
FZB	Forschungszentrum Bodenfruchtbarkeit Müncheberg/ Research Center for Soil Fertility
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility: https://www.gbif.org
GD-NW	Geologischer Dienst NRW/ Geological Survey of North Rhine-Westphalia: https://www.gd.nrw.de
HLNUG	Hessisches Landesamt für Naturschutz, Umwelt und Geologie/ State Office for Nature protection, Environment and Geology: https://www.hlnug.de

ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System: www.icos-ri.eu
IIASA	International Institute for Applied system Analysis: www.iiasa.ac.at
ISCN	International Soil Carbon Network: http://iscn.fluxdata.org
ISMN	International Soil Moisture Network: https://ismn.geo.tuwien.ac.at/
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre: https://www.isric.online
JRC	Joint Research Centre (European Commission): https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en
KA4 / KA5	Bodenkundliche Kartieranleitung/ Manual of soil mapping 4th/5th Ed.
LABO	Länderarbeitsgemeinschaft Boden: https://www.labo-deutschland.de
LAGB	Landesamt für Geologie und Bergwesen Sachsen-Anhalt/ State Office for Geology and Mining: https://lagb.sachsen-anhalt.de
LANUV	Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz Nordrhein-Westfalen/ State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer protection: https://www.lanuv.nrw.de
LAU	Landesamt für Umweltschutz Sachsen-Anhalt/ State Office for Environmental Protection: https://lau.sachsen-anhalt.de
LBEG	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geologie/ State Office for Mining, Energy and Geology Lower Saxony: www.lbeg.niedersachsen.de
LBGR	Landesamt für Bergbau, Geologie und Rohstoffe Brandenburg/ State Office for Mining, Geology and Resources Brandenburg: https://lbgr.brandenburg.de
LfL	Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft/ Bavarian State Office for Agriculture: https://www.lfl.bayern.de
LfU-BB	Landesamt für Umwelt Brandenburg/ State Office for Environment Brandenburg: https://lfu.brandenburg.de
LfU-BW	Landesanstalt für Umweltschutz Baden Württemberg
LfU-BY	Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt/ Bavarian State Office for Environment: https://www.lfu.bayern.de
LfULG	Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie/ Saxonian State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology: http://www.lfulg.sachsen.de
LGB	Landesamt für Geologie und Bergbau Rheinland-Pfalz/ State Office for Geology and Mining Rhineland-Palatinate: http://www.lgb-rlp.de

LGB-BB	Landesvermessung und Geobasisinformation Brandenburg/ State Agency for Land Survey and Geoinformation Brandenburg: https://www.geobasis-bb.de/
LGRB	Landesamt für Geologie, Rohstoffe und Bergbau Baden-Württemberg/ State Office for Geology, Resources and Mining Baden-Wuerttemberg: http://www.lgrb-bw.de
LLUR	Landesamt für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und ländliche Räume Schleswig-Holstein/ State Office for Agriculture, Environment and Rural areas Schleswig-Holstein: https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/Landesregierung/LLUR/llur_node.html
LUA	Landesamt für Umwelt und Arbeitsschutz Saarland/ State Office for Environment Saarland: https://www.saarland.de/SID-012CD120-4285AC49/landesamt_umwelt_arbeitsschutz.htm
LUBW	Landesamt für Umwelt, Messungen und Naturschutz Baden-Württemberg/ State Office for Environment, Measurement and Nature Conservation Baden-Wuerttemberg: https://www.lubw.baden-wuerttemberg.de
LUNG	Landesamt für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Geologie Mecklenburg-Vorpommerns/ State Office for Nature conservation, Environment and Geology: https://www.lung.mv-regierung.de
LVerGeo- RP	Landesamt für Vermessung und Geobasisinformation Rheinland-Pfalz/ State Office for Survey and Geoinformation Rhineland-Palatinate: https://lvermgeo.rlp.de
LVGL-SL	Saarlaendischen Landesamt für Vermessung, Geoinformation und Landentwicklung/ State Office for Surveying, Geoinformation and Rural Development: https://www.saarland.de/vermessung_geoinformation_landentwicklung.htm
MetOffice	Hadley Centre for Climate Prediction and Research - Met Office: https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/climate-guide/science/science-behind-climate-change/hadley
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration: https://earthdata.nasa.gov
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development: http://www.oecd.org/
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium: http://www.opengeospatial.org/
ORNL DAAC	The Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center for biogeochemical dynamics
SGD	Staatliche Geologische Dienste der Länder / Federal Geological Surveys of the States: http://www.infogeo.de
SGN	Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung: http://www.senckenberg.de
SOTER	Soil and Terrain Database: https://www.isric.online/explore/soter

- TI Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institute/ Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries: <https://www.thuenen.de/>
- TLL Thüringer Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft/ Thuringian Regional Office for Agriculture: <https://www.thueringen.de/th9/tll/>
- TLUG Thüringer Landesanstalt für Umwelt und Geologie/ Thuringian Regional Office for Environment and Geology: <https://www.thueringen.de/th8/tlug/>
- TU Wien Vienna University of Technology, Department for Geodesy and Geoinformation: <https://www.geo.tuwien.ac.at/>
- UBA Umweltbundesamt/ German Environment Agency: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/>
- WRB World Reference Base: <http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/soil-survey/soil-classification/world-reference-base/en/>
- ZALF Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung e.V./ Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research e.V.: <http://www.zalf.de>

Glossary

BGR Produktcenter is the infrastructure for the provision of geodata produced or partly produced by the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR): <https://produktcenter.bgr.de>

Bodenkundliche Landesaufnahme is the general term for inner state programs of the German Federal States with the aim of state-wide surveying and describing the soils, their horizons and properties and their distribution. The survey is implemented by soil sampling (and laboratory analysis afterwards) and profile and site description by standardized or at least consistent methods.

Bodenschätzung is a national German soil taxation framework to numerically record the soil productivity of arable and grassland soils in a value (Blume et al., 2016). It was introduced in Germany in the 1930s (*Reichsbodenschätzung*) and continued after 1945 in West Germany and after 1990 in East Germany for the taxation of agricultural soils (German soil taxation law – *Bodenschätzungsgesetz* from 1934-19-16, last revision from 2007-12-20). Based on the characteristics of soil type, origin and status level, two soil values for arable land, *Bodenzahl* and *Ackerzahl*, are determined. These are maintained in the *Official Property Cadastre Information System* (ALKIS) for the land use parcels concerned which is managed by the states' tax offices. The Geological Survey of Lower Saxony (LBEG) developed a translations tool of the soil taxation values into the nomenclature of the 4th ed. of the German Soil Survey Guideline (Bartsch et al., 2003). This tool has some limitation according the soil texture, e.g. overrated the silt content to the expense of sand (Hangen and Förster, 2013).

DWD Open Data Server is a data infrastructure of the Germany Weather Service to follow its legal mandate of providing weather and climate data free of charge. The server presents current weather forecast data (../weather/) and is linked with the DWD Climate Data Center (CLC) (../climate/) which stores German and European climate data (see also: <https://www.dwd.de/DE/leistungen/cdcftp/cdcftp.html>). The forecast data include weather alerts, results of global and regional forecast models (../icon/; ../cosmo_de/), local forecasts per weather station and national radar products.

European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) is the thematic centre for soil related data in Europe, and one part of the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. The aim of the ESDAC is to be the central reference point for relevant soil data at European level. The centre provides datasets, map application and services as well as scientific reports. It is also the European link to networks and initiatives at the international level.

FAO Soils Portal is the soil data infrastructure of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. It includes global maps and data about soil quality, soil properties, land use, slope (Harmonized World Soil Database v1.2). The portal provides access to the FAO/UNESCO Soil Map of the World 1:5,000,000. See also <http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/>.

Forstliche Standortskartierung is the term for the forest site survey program of the German federal states for the purpose to assess the suitability for forestry use (AK Standortskartierung, 2016). This includes the survey of growing conditions according to climate, relief, vegetation, and hydrological and soil conditions. The survey concepts of the federal states vary. Petzold et al. (2016) give a detailed overview of the states' programs characteristics and the collected primary soil information. Generally, the survey shall include the total forest sites of the state (actually, this is the case only in Hesse) (Petzold et al., 2016).

Geoportal.de (GDI-DE) is a product of the Spatial Data Infrastructure Germany (GDI-DE) which networks official data from the Federal Government, the states and municipalities of Germany. It provides a service for searching specialist spatial data and visualization with an interactive map.

Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is an international open data infrastructure for the topics biodiversity, biology and species related data. GBIF arose from a recommendation of the OECD and was officially established in 2001 through Memorandum of Understanding between participating governments, which fund the portal. It offers free access for all records published via the network. The data can be explored by occurrences, species, datasets and countries. Further, GBIF offers tools for publishing data. As Germany is a founding and funding member of GBIF, it has also an own representative office (<http://www.gbif.de/>).

Global Soil Information System (GLOSIS) was established by the Global Soil Partnership (GSP, <http://www.fao.org/globalsoilpartnership/en/>) in 2012. This inter-governmental network is closely related to the network of the FAO and its members for FAOSTAT. Each national institution has the task to develop and share national data. The goal is to establish SoilSTAT as an international spatial data infrastructure linked with national spatial infrastructures.

INSPIRE geoportal offers the possibility to search spatial datasets, geodata services as well as access restrictions of spatial datasets from the EU member states within the framework of the INSPIRE Directive (EU, 2007). INSPIRE shall facilitate the cross-border use of spatial data within the European Union. INSPIRE requires from the providing state agencies standardized metadata (ISO 19115) as well as the provision of these descriptions on the Internet, including discovery, view and download services. The data itself, too, must be available in a uniform format.

International Soil Modelling Consortium (ISMC) provides a data platform specifically for modellers, from the lab scale to the global scale. Further ISMC links many projects and initiatives in the field of soil modelling. The website offers an overview of data bases sorted by scale (Site/Lysimetric scale data, catchment scale data, basin to continental/global scale data, global data networks). The ISMC provides a model collection for the topics hydrology, soil physics, pedogenesis, crop, biochemistry, plant-soil, functional-structural-plant model and ecology.

International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC) was founded in 1966 through the International Soil Science Society (ISSS) and United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), today operating under the name ISRIC - World Soil Information. Its mission is to serve the international community with information about the world's soil resources to help addressing major global issues. ISRIC operates on three priority areas: - soil data and soil mapping - application of soil data in global development issues - training and education. ISRIC is a regular member of the ICSU World Data System and hosts the World Data Centre for Soils since 1989. The database hosts 105 datasets and data bases (2017-12-08), including the WoSIS soil profile database, the SOTER maps at the national level, the SoilGrids at the current resolution of 250 m, the WISE databases like the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) at the scale of 30"x30" and, finally, the spatial data of the 1:M FAO Soil Map of the World respectively used to fill gaps in SOTER databases (so-called SOTWIS databases), using the FAO soil classification.

Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) is an international non-profit organization to develop and establish quality open standards in a consensus process for the global geospatial community.

SOTER -Soil and Terrain Database was initiated in 1986 by the FAO, the United Nations Environmental Programme and ISRIC, under the umbrella of the International Soil Science Society. The aim of the programme was to develop a global SOTER database at scale 1:1 million as a pre-step of the FAO-UNESCO Soil Map of the World. A SOTER database with global coverage was never achieved, but SOTER databases were developed for various regions, countries and continents. Derived from the SOTER databases are the SOTWIS databases for gap-filling the incomplete soil profile information of the SOTER database (van Engelen and Dijkshoorn, 2013; Batjes, 2017).

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